

Norwegian University of
Science and Technology

Interaction of Eutectic Fe-Si-B Alloy with Graphite Crucibles

Bettina Grorud

Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology

Submission date: June 2018

Supervisor: Merete Tangstad, IMA

Co-supervisor: Jafar Safarian, IMA

Norwegian University of Science and Technology
Department of Materials Science and Engineering

*"Nothing is as easy as it looks.
Everything takes longer than you think.
Anything that can go wrong will go wrong."
- Murphy's law*

Preface

This master's thesis describes the investigation on how eutectic Fe-Si-B alloys interacts with dense graphite crucibles at temperatures around the eutectic point. The work has been carried out within the framework of the EU-project, AMADEUS, and is the evaluation basis for the course *TMT9000 Materials Chemistry and Energy Technology, Master's Thesis*, at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, NTNU.

AMADEUS has received funds from the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation program, FET-OPEN action, under grant agreement 737054. The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither the REA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The main results and ideas behind this master's thesis may be regarded as a successor to the specialisation project "Interaction of Liquid Si-B Alloys with Graphite Crucibles" performed by the author during the summer and fall of 2017 at NTNU. Accordingly, some sections of this master's thesis are taken from that work.

First and foremost, I would like to thank my supervisor, Prof. Merete Tangstad (NTNU) for the opportunity to work on this project. She has always been available for discussions and questions, and has provided me with insightful opinions along the way. I would also like to thank my co-supervisor, Assoc. Prof. Jafar Safarian, NTNU, and PhD candidate Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, for helpful input throughout this work.

I would like to thank Senior Engineer Dmitry Slizovskiy, NTNU, and Senior Engineer Jonas Einan Gjøvik, NTNU, for valuable help and guidance during the challenges that occurred along the way. Special gratitude is expressed towards PhD candidate Ivar Andre Ødegård, NTNU, for preparing the master alloy with me and for always being available for questions regarding the furnace.

Further, I would like to thank Senior Engineer Morten Peder Raanes, NTNU, for performing the EPMA analysis, Research Scientist Sarina Bao, SINTEF Industry, for performing

the wetting tests, and Research Scientist Julian Tolchard, SINTEF Industry, for performing the XRD-analysis.

Lastly, I would like to thank "Hydrogenjentene" for the invaluable memories made through these past five years, and Zacharias Murad for all your love and support.

Summary

The work in this thesis was performed as a part of the AMADEUS project¹. The goal was to experimentally investigate the interaction between eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy and dense graphite crucibles, and the results will be compared to previous work performed by the author (2017)^{[28] [29]} on eutectic Si-B alloy. The results will be used to ultimately decide if eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy in graphite crucibles is suitable for application in latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) systems.

The experiments were performed on eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy with a composition of 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si, and 9 wt.% B, contained in dense graphite crucibles. The experimental work was conducted in a resistance heated furnace in 5N Ar (g) atmosphere, in which three different types of experiments were performed:

- The samples were subjected to 20 °C above the melting temperature for 1 h, before one or two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C were initiated.
- The samples were subjected to 1550 °C for 1 h, before one or two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C were initiated.
- The samples were subjected to 1550 °C for 1 h, before one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100$ °C was initiated.

The characterisation of the samples was mainly performed by light optical microscopy (LOM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and electron probe micro-analyser (EPMA). Wetting tests of Fe-Si-B alloy on graphite and alumina were also performed.

It was found that very little silicon had penetrated into the crucible to form SiC, while significant penetration was observed in the previous work performed by the author. This indicates that eutectic Fe-Si-B has a lower degrading effect on the crucible compared to eutectic Si-B alloy, which is desirable for the intended application.

¹<http://amadeus-project.eu>

No continuous SiC barrier layer was observed in any of the samples containing Fe-Si-B alloy. Some single SiC and B₄C particles were observed along the edges of the alloy, in addition to a eutectic B_{4+δ}C phase in several areas of the alloy. The total amount of carbon present in the eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy still appeared to be lower compared to eutectic Si-B alloy, and it can thus be assumed that the Fe-Si-B alloy will remain more stable with time compared to the Si-B alloy.

The wettability of the Fe-Si-B alloy on graphite was found to be high, with a measured contact angle of approx. 30°. High wettability might result in more penetration of silicon in the crucible, and consequently faster degradation of the crucible. However, since very little penetration of silicon was observed in the crucible, the high wettability will most likely not be a challenge in the intended application.

The wettability of the Fe-Si-B alloy on alumina was found to be low, with measured contact angles of approx. 120°. This, in addition to low reactivity between the materials, indicates that alumina might be a possible alternative crucible material for eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy in the intended application.

Unlike the Si-B alloy, the volume of the Fe-Si-B alloy was found to be shrinking during solidification. This is a desirable material property for the intended application due to previous challenges caused by volume expansion during solidification of the alloy.

Five different phases were identified by EPMA analysis. This includes FeB and Si₄BFe₄ as matrices, SiB₆ and Si₂B₅Fe₂ as eutectic phases, and SiC particles located at the edge of the samples. It is uncertain if the two three-component phases, Si₄BFe₄ and Si₂B₅Fe₂, were metastable or if they were stable due to carbon saturation of the system. Two modifications of boron carbide were found, namely B₄C and B_{4+δ}C. B₄C was formed as particles in the same areas as SiC, while B_{4+δ}C appeared to be a eutectic phase. The B_{4+δ}C was found to contain more boron compared to B₄C, in addition to slightly more aluminium impurities.

The fusion enthalpy of Fe-Si-B with 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si, and 9 wt.% B was calculated

in FactSage to be 3.67 kJ/cm^3 . This is slightly lower than for eutectic Si-B, which has a fusion enthalpy of 4.42 kJ/cm^3 , but still sufficiently high for the intended application.

The samples in the wetting tests showed signs of melting in the range between 1200-1250 °C, and the slight deviation from the theoretical melting temperature is considered to be due to carbon saturation.

The obtained composition of the master alloy was confirmed to be close to the ideal composition by ICP-MS analysis. Other than the alloying elements, only very small concentrations of Al and Mn were detected. The results obtained in this work are thus considered to be representative for eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy with a composition of 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.%Si, and 9 wt.% B.

The overall results indicate that eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy with the composition of 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.%Si, and 9 wt.% B is highly suitable for the application as phase change material in latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) systems. The results also indicate that alumina might be a possible alternative crucible material for the intended application.

Sammendrag

Arbeidet i denne avhandlingen ble utført som en del av AMADEUS prosjektet². Målet med oppgaven var å eksperimentelt utforske interaksjonen mellom eutektisk Fe-Si-B legering og grafittdigler, og resultatene vil bli sammenlignet med tidligere arbeid utført av forfatteren (2017)^{[28][29]} på eutektisk Si-B legering. Resultatene vil til slutt benyttes for å bestemme om eutektisk Fe-Si-B legering i grafittdigler er egnet for bruk i "Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage" systemer.

Eksperimentene ble utført på eutektisk Fe-Si-B legering, med en sammensetning av 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si og 9 wt.% B, i grafittdigler. Det eksperimentelle arbeidet ble utført i en motstands-oppvarmet ovn i 5N Ar (g) atmosfære, der tre forskjellige typer eksperimenter ble utført:

- Prøvene ble holdt ved 20 °C over smeltetemperaturen i 1 t, før én eller to temperatursykluser mellom $T_m \pm 20$ °C ble startet.
- Prøvene ble holdt ved 1550 °C i 1 t, før én eller to temperatursykluser mellom $T_m \pm 20$ °C ble startet.
- Prøvene ble holdt ved 1550 °C i 1 t, før én temperatursyklus mellom $T_m \pm 100$ °C ble startet.

Karakteriseringen av prøvene ble hovedsakelig utført i lysmikroskopi (LOM), scanning elektronmikroskopi (SEM) og elektronmikrosonde (EPMA). Fuktnings tester av Fe-Si-B legering på grafitt og alumina ble også utført.

Det ble funnet at svært lite silisium hadde penetrert digelen for å danne SiC, mens betydelig penetrasjon ble observert i tidligere arbeid utført av forfatteren. Dette indikerer at eutektisk Fe-Si-B har lavere nedbrytningseffekt på digelen sammenlignet med eutektisk Si-B legering, noe som er fordelaktig for det tiltenkte bruksområdet.

²<http://amadeus-project.eu>

Det ble ikke observert et kontinuerlig SiC barrierelag i noen av prøvene som inneholdt Fe-Si-B legering. Noen enkeltstående SiC og B₄C partikler ble observert langs kanten av legeringen, men det totale innholdet av karbon i legeringen virket å være lavere for eutektisk Fe-Si-B legering sammenlignet med eutektisk Si-B legering. Det ser derfor ut til at Fe-Si-B legeringen vil holde seg mer stabil over tid sammenlignet med Si-B legeringen.

Fuktningsgraden av Fe-Si-B legeringen på grafitt ble funnet å være høy, med en kontaktvinkel på omtrent 30°. Høy fuktningsgrad kan resultere i mer penetrasjon av silisium inn i digelen, og dermed også raskere nedbrytning av digelen. Etersom veldig lite penetrasjon av silisium ble observert i digelen antas det at den høye fuktningsgraden mest sannsynligvis ikke kommer til å være en utfordring i det tiltenkte bruksområdet.

Fuktningsgraden av Fe-Si-B legeringen på alumina ble funnet å være lav, med en kontaktvinkel på omtrent 120°. Dette, i tillegg til lav reaktivitet mellom materialene, indikerer at alumina er et mulig alternativt digelmateriale for eutektisk Fe-Si-B legering i det tiltenkte bruksområdet.

I motsetning til Si-B legeringen krympet volumet av Fe-Si-B legeringen under størkning. Dette regnes som en ettertraktet egenskap, ettersom det tidligere har vært utfordringer knyttet til volumekspansjon under størkning av legeringen.

Fem forskjellige faser ble identifisert ved EPMA-analyse. Dette inkluderer FeB og Si₄BFe₄ som matrisefaser, SiB₆ og Si₂B₅Fe₂ som eutektiske faser og SiC-partikler ved kanten av prøvene. Det er usikkert om de to trekomponentfasene Si₄BFe₄ og Si₂B₅Fe₂ var metastabile, eller om de var stabile på grunn av karbonmetting av systemet. Det ble funnet to modifikasjoner av borkarbid. B₄C ble funnet i samme områder som SiC, mens B_{4+δ}C så ut til å være utfelt som eutektisk fase. B_{4+δ}C hadde et høyere borinnhold enn B₄C, i tillegg til en noe høyere konsentrasjon av aluminium urenheter.

Fusjonsentalpien av Fe-Si-B legering med sammensetning på 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si og 9 wt.% B ble beregnet i FactSage til å være 3.67 kJ/cm³. Dette er en noe lavere verdi enn for Si-B, som har en fusjonsentalpi på 4.42 kJ/cm³, men fortsatt høyt nok for det

tiltenkte bruksområdet.

Prøvene i fuktningstestene viste tegn til smelting i området mellom 1200-1250 °C, og det lille avviket fra teoretisk smeltetemperatur regnes å være grunnet karbonmetting.

Den oppnådde sammensetningen av masterlegeringen ble bekreftet å være nært den ideelle sammensetningen ved ICP-MS analyse. Annet enn legeringselementene ble kun svært små konsentrasjoner av Al og Mn detektert. Resultatene oppnådd i dette arbeidet anses derfor å være representative for eutektisk Fe-Si-B legering med en sammensetning av 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si og 9 wt.% B.

De samlede resultatene indikerer at eutektisk Fe-Si-B legering med en sammensetning av 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si og 9 wt.% B er svært godt egnet til bruk som faseendrende materiale i "Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage" systemer. Resultatene indikerer også at alumina kan vise seg å være et alternativt digelmateriale i det tiltenkte bruksområdet.

List of Abbreviations

Al₂O₃ Alumina

At.% Atomic percent

BSE Backscattered electron

B Boron

CIP Cold isostatic pressing

C Carbon

EDS Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy

EPMA Electron probe micro-analysis

HSU Heat storage unit

ICP-MS Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry

LHTES Latent heat thermal energy storage

LOM Light optical microscopy

Na Sodium

PCM Phase change material

RSD Relative standard deviation

SEM Scanning electron microscopy

SE Secondary electron

SiC Silicon carbide

Si Silicon

TIPV converter Thermionic-photovoltaic converter

TPV converter Thermophotovoltaic converter

Wt.% Weight percent

XRD X-ray diffraction

Nomenclature

β -SiC Cubic low temperature phase of SiC

α -SiC Hexagonal high temperature phase of SiC

γ_{LV} The surface tension between a liquid and vapour phase

γ_{SL} The surface tension between a solid and a liquid phase

γ_{SV} The surface tension between a solid and vapour phase

θ_{con} Contact angle

ΔG_v Gibbs free energy associated with volume

ΔG_i Gibbs free energy associated with interface

ΔG Gibbs free energy

Δg Gibbs free energy per unit volume

ΔH_v Enthalpy of solidification

Δs_f	Entropy of fusion per unit volume
ΔT	Undercooling temperature
C	Number of components in a system
D	Lateral penetration depth
F	Degrees of freedom in a system
$H_{fus,x}$	Fusion enthalpy of each element
H	Vertical penetration depth
P	Number of phases in thermodynamic equilibrium in a system
r^*	Critical radius
r	Radius of the nucleus
T_m	Melting temperature
V_l	Average volume of the alloy in liquid state
V_s	Average volume of the alloy in solid state
$V_{s,x}$	Volume of each element in solid state
Z	Atomic number

Contents

Preface	iii
Summary	v
Sammendrag	ix
Symbols and abbreviations	xiii
1 Introduction	1
2 Theory	7
2.1 Carbon as crucible material for phase change materials	7
2.2 Nucleation theory	8
2.2.1 Classical nucleation theory	9
2.3 Wetting	11
2.4 The Si-B-C-Fe system and its subsystems	12
2.4.1 The Si-C binary system	13
2.4.2 The Si-B binary system	30
2.4.3 The B-C binary system	32
2.4.4 The Si-B-C ternary system	33
2.4.5 The Fe-Si binary system	34
2.4.6 The Fe-C binary system	41
2.4.7 The Fe-B binary system	42
2.4.8 The Si-Fe-B ternary system	43
3 Experimental	45
3.1 Composition of the alloy	45
3.2 Raw materials	50
3.3 Apparatus	51
3.3.1 Crucibles	51
3.3.2 Induction furnace	53
3.3.3 Graphite tube furnace	54

3.3.4	Thermogradient	56
3.3.5	Cutting	57
3.3.6	Mounting	59
3.3.7	Grinding and polishing	59
3.3.8	Characterisation	60
3.4	Preparation of Master alloy	64
3.5	Wetting properties	65
3.6	Experimental log	65
3.7	Method	71
4	Results	75
4.1	ICP-MS	75
4.2	EPMA	76
4.3	SEM analysis	106
4.4	LOM analysis	109
4.5	Wetting tests	118
4.6	Mass loss	131
4.7	Experimental challenges	133
5	Discussion	139
6	Conclusion	151
7	References	155
	Appendices	161
A	XRD analysis	161
B	Images obtained in LOM	163
B.1	2.5x magnification	164
B.2	10x magnification	173
C	Images obtained in SEM	185
C.1	Samples subjected to one temperature cycle	185
C.2	Samples subjected to two temperature cycles	189

C.3	Samples subjected to a larger temperature interval	192
-----	--	-----

1 Introduction

Development of energy saving technologies and technologies based on non-combustible renewable energy sources are widely focused on by governments in countries all over the world. Thermal energy storage is one of the main fields investigated in development of such technologies, where the key element is to improve efficiency of thermal energy utilisation during storage^[40]. An example is AMADEUS, a research project funded by the European Commission for the development of a new generation of ultra-compact energy storage devices based on molten metals and solid state heat-to-power converters^[2].

A possible method to store thermal energy is by exploitation of latent heat in materials, where heat may be absorbed or released without a change in temperature. When a phase transition takes place within the system, the heat simply transforms a portion of the substance, e.g. from solid to liquid. Such materials are referred to as phase change materials (PCMs), and latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) systems utilise this heat of fusion in certain materials by employing energy to cause the phase changing transitions.

Phase change materials have the ability to store relatively large amounts of energy in small volumes, providing some of the lowest storage material costs per unit energy. Most phase change materials operate between solid-liquid transformations, and they are therefore suitable for applications in indirect storage concepts^[42]. Potential fields of application of phase change materials are in electricity production on solar thermal power stations that demands heat storage units (HSUs) with high reliability and thermal efficiency, in addition to low cost.

The AMADEUS project aim at realising the proof of concept of these extremely compact LHTES devices with unprecedented high energy densities^[2]. In the system presented in Figure 1.1, energy will be stored in the form of heat in the phase change material, and electricity will be produced upon demand using novel solid-state heat-to-power converters based on photovoltaic and thermionic effects. In the charge-cycle, practically any kind of energy input can be employed for melting the phase change material and the energy is stored as latent heat at high temperatures. In the discharge-cycle, the stored latent heat

is transferred to the thermionic-photovoltaic (TIPV) converter^[3]. This type of converter comprises three elements: the emitter, the collector, and the thermophotovoltaic (TPV) energy converter. The emitter is a refractory material that reaches high temperature upon external heating and subsequently radiates electrons and photons. The electrons are absorbed by the collector, while the photons pass through. The photons will then reach the TPV cell, where they are converted into electricity^[17].

Figure 1.1: Schematic figure of the system to be developed in the AMADEUS project. The system consists of a vessel, a TIPV converter, and a phase change material. The figure is adapted from AMADEUS^[3].

An important technological challenge in the AMADEUS project is to find the most suitable phase change material for the system. The heat of fusion of materials commonly increase with melting temperature, as seen in Figure 1.2, and it would thus be reasonable to investigate higher melting point phase change materials. Implementation of heat storage units with high-temperature phase change materials will allow a considerable raise in the efficiency of using thermal and solar energy^[40].

Figure 1.2: The figure displays the latent heat of fusion of different materials as a function of melting temperature. The values are taken from SI Chemical Data^[5], and the compounds in the legend are listed with decreasing value of latent heat.

In addition to high latent heat, other significant properties include high specific thermal capacity, heat of fusion, and density to provide minimum size of the heat storage unit. The material should melt congruently, which means that the phase change material should keep stoichiometric composition in solid and liquid conditions, with reliable convertibility at repeated phase transformations. The heat conductivity should also be high, which will provide minimum temperature gradients demanded for charging and discharging of the heat storage unit. Other properties such as non-toxicity, flame and fire safety, availability and cheapness should also be taken into account^[40].

According to the research done by Datas *et al.* (2016)^[19], silicon is particularly interesting due to its high melting point (1410 °C), high latent heat (1800 J/g or 500 Wh/kg), thermal conductivity (25 W/mK), low cost (less than \$2/kg or \$4/kWh), and abundance on earth. However, experiments on molten silicon for solar thermal energy storage performed at the University of South California by Gilpin (2015)^[51] revealed some challenges with this material selection. The most relevant engineering concerned related to the material was the damage on the container due to the volume expansion of pure silicon during solidification. Datas *et al.* (2016)^[19] found that the most reasonable solution is to use silicon alloys instead of pure silicon to reduce the freezing expansion coefficient of the phase change material.

The silicon-boron system has been investigated for use in LHTES systems by several companies all over the world, such as 1414 Degrees^[1], SILSTORE Energy^[63], and Ferroatlantica^[26]. This system is found to be particularly interesting due to the extremely high latent heat (4650 J/g) of boron, in addition to the moderately low melting temperature (1385 °C) of the eutectic $\text{Si}_{0.92}\text{B}_{0.08}$. There are, however, some scientific and technical challenges that need to be overcome in this system as well. A practical concern by utilising this system is the thermo-chemical compatibility between the crucible and the phase change material at such high temperatures. This problem largely originates from the extremely high reactivity of molten silicon with carbon, which in addition is enhanced by the presence of boron. Another challenge with this system is the high volume expansion during solidification, which, as earlier mentioned, might damage the containers when the system is applied on an industrial scale. The author investigated the interaction between eutectic Si-B alloy and graphite crucibles during the summer and autumn of 2017^[28]^[29]. It was found that silicon had penetrated the crucible and formed SiC in all samples, in addition to the formation of a SiC barrier layer along the entire interface between the alloy and the crucibles. A possible solution to this challenge is to introduce other alloying elements to the system, to reduce the reactivity between the alloy and the container material. The new alloy should have a comparable enthalpy of fusion to eutectic Si-B and better thermal conductivity, while lower volume expansion during solidification is preferred.

This work will be performed as a part of the AMADEUS project³, and the main objective is to experimentally investigate the interactions between dense graphite crucibles and a eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy during repeated temperature cycles around the eutectic temperature. The results will ultimately be used to determine if this system is suitable for application in LHTES systems. The different phases obtained, the distribution and location of these phases, and to which extent the crucibles react with the alloy will be investigated and characterised by light optical microscopy (LOM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

The work will be outlined by first presenting important theory and existing literature in the field, followed by an experimental section which describes the scope of the experiments

³<http://amadeus-project.eu>

and characterisations performed. Further, the experimental results and a discussion of these are presented. Lastly, the conclusion section highlights the most important results.

2 Theory

The goal of this study is to investigate the interaction between eutectic Si-B-Fe alloy and dense graphite crucibles around the eutectic temperature. In order to gain an understanding of this, it is important to have knowledge of the systems in consideration and existing literature in the field. This section will provide an introduction to why graphite crucibles are suitable for the intended application, nucleation theory, and wetting theory, in addition to giving a basic understanding of the phase diagrams and thermodynamics of the reactions in the system. An overview of the existing literature and research in the field is also included.

2.1 Carbon as crucible material for phase change materials

Carbon in the form of graphite is widely used in a variety of industries, such as solar cell silicon, semi-conductor industry, and other renewable industries^[18]. The material has a planar, layered structure that consists of carbon atoms arranged in a honeycomb lattice. The layers are weakly bonded by Van der Waal forces, which allows them to easily separate or to slide past each other. The carbon atoms in the planes are covalently bonded, where three or four of the potential bonding sites are satisfied. The fourth electron is free to migrate in the plane, which makes the material electrically conductive.

Graphite is highly anisotropic due to the different type of bindings in two crystallographic directions, which will create some challenges in design and use. However, by applying cold isostatic pressing (CIP) to micro particles of graphite, an isotropic structure can be obtained as seen in Figure 2.1.

(a) Image of conventional anisotropic graphite. The structure is clearly directionally dependant.

(b) Image of isotropic high density graphite. The structure is clearly uniform in all orientations.

Figure 2.1: Images show anisotropic and isotropic graphite supplied by Toyo Tanso^[68].

This form of graphite has stable properties and a finer structure than conventional graphite, as well as being able to withstand long time use at high temperatures exceeding 2000 °C. Isotropic graphite also possess properties such as low thermal expansion ($4.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$)^[69] and a high coefficient of thermal conductivity ($140 \text{ W}/(\text{m} \cdot \text{K})$)^[69], which is important to obtain a good thermal shock resistance and heat distribution^[18]. Due to the combination of these properties, isotropic graphite is considered very interesting for the application as a container for LHTES systems.

2.2 Nucleation theory

In LHTES systems, the temperature will be varied in cycles around the eutectic point of the phase change material. During solidification of the alloy, nucleation will occur and a secondary phase (solid) will form in the primary phase (liquid). This process will take place even above the equilibrium melting temperature, but the nuclei will not be stable at this point. However, the likelihood of forming a stable nuclei will increase as the temperature decreases below the melting temperature. The temperature difference between the melting temperature of a material and the temperature at which a stable nucleus form is referred to as the nucleation undercooling.^[70]

2.2.1 Classical nucleation theory

The theory presented in this section is adapted from Undheim (2018)^[70]. Classical nucleation theory is the most common theoretical model used to describe the behaviour of the nucleation of a new thermodynamic phase. Figure 2.2a present the thermal history of a typical solidification process. Stable nuclei are formed below the melting temperature, indicated by ΔT in the figure. Figure 2.2b shows the rate of nucleation, I , and number of grains, N , as a function of the temperature profile presented in Figure 2.2a. It can be observed that the nucleation rate is zero until the nucleation undercooling, ΔT , is achieved. At this point, the cooling will slow down due to the release of latent heat from the formation of the solid phase. When the nucleation rate is at its maximum, the latent heat released is greater than the cooling and the melt is no longer decreasing in temperature. As a result, the nucleation rate rapidly drops to zero, indicated by the second vertical lines in Figure 2.2. The final grain population is quickly established afterwards.

(a) Schematic presentation of the temperature profile for a typical solidification process. The dotted line indicates the start of nucleation, ΔT is the nucleation undercooling, and t_f is the time from the first nucleus appears until solidification is complete.

(b) Schematic presentation of the nucleation rate, I , and number of grains, N , as a function of time.

Figure 2.2: Schematic presentations of the classical nucleation theory. The figures are taken from Undheim (2018)^[70].

In order for the nucleation to occur, the change in free energy, ΔG , must be negative, i.e.:

$$\frac{d(\Delta G(r))}{dr} < 0 \quad (2.1)$$

where r is the radius of the nucleus. The change in free energy is composed of two terms, the Gibbs free energy associated with the interface, ΔG_i , and with the volume, ΔG_v . Assuming a spherical cap model, ΔG can be expressed as:

$$\Delta G = \gamma_{SL}4\pi r^2 + \frac{\Delta g 4\pi r^3}{3} \quad (2.2)$$

where γ_{SL} is the solid/liquid interface energy, r is the radius of the nucleus, and Δg is the Gibbs free energy difference between the liquid and solid per unit volume. For a system where the undercooling is low, in addition to a low difference in heat capacity between liquid and solid, Δg can be approximated as:

$$\Delta g = \Delta s_f \Delta T \quad (2.3)$$

where Δs_f is the entropy of fusion per unit volume, which is negative in the case of solidification, and ΔT is the undercooling, which is positive for temperatures below the melting temperature. Therefore, ΔG is strictly positive for temperatures above T_m .

When the temperature is decreased below the melting point, $T < T_m$, the sign of the second term of Equation 2.3 will change as Δg is negative below the melting temperature. In this case, ΔG will have a maximum which can be regarded as a energy barrier that must be overcome in order to stabilise the nucleus. At the maximum, the change in free energy will be zero, $\frac{d(\Delta G(r))}{dr} = 0$. This corresponds to a minimum possible radius, above which the nuclei is stable. This critical radius can be expressed as:

$$r^* = \frac{2\gamma_{sl}T_m}{\Delta T \Delta H_v} \quad (2.4)$$

where ΔH_v is the enthalpy of solidification.

The situation above describes homogeneous nucleation, where nuclei are formed spontaneously in a homogeneous system. This form of nucleation is very rare and without practical importance. In contrast, heterogeneous nucleation describes the situation where

the nucleus forms on a solid substrate in the liquid. This solid substrate can either be particles dispersed in the liquid or contact with the crucible or an oxide layer. Heterogeneous nucleation reduces the energy barrier that is necessary to overcome in order to stabilise the nucleus from a purely geometric point of view, as fewer atoms are needed to form a sphere of radius, r . For heterogeneous nucleation, the change in Gibbs free energy, ΔG , is modified by the factor:

$$f(\theta_{con}) = \frac{(2 + \cos \theta_{con})(1 - \cos \theta_{con})^2}{4} \quad (2.5)$$

where θ_{con} is the contact angle, which describes the angle between the solid nucleus and the substrate. The concept of wetting will be further described in Section 2.3. There are two extreme cases of Equation 2.5, defined as:

$$\theta_{con} = 0^\circ \Rightarrow f = 0 \quad (2.6)$$

and

$$\theta_{con} = 180^\circ \Rightarrow f = 1 \quad (2.7)$$

In the first case, there is no nucleation barrier and the solid nucleus is completely wetting the surface. In the latter case there is no decrease in energy barrier, and the situation corresponds to homogeneous nucleation. How SiC particles formed in silicon affect undercooling will be discussed in Section 2.4.1.2.

2.3 Wetting

When a liquid is brought in contact with a solid surface, intermolecular interactions between the two will ensure that contact is maintained. This ability is referred to as wetting, which is usually characterised by the contact angle, θ_{con} , formed at the gas-liquid-solid interface. Wettability is defined as the degree of wetting, which is determined by the force balance between adhesive and cohesive forces between a liquid and a solid. Adhesive forces will cause the liquid drop to spread out on the surface, while cohesive forces within the droplet will cause it to maintain a ball shape and try to avoid contact with the surface^[20]. The relationship between the contact angle and the surface tension

can be described by Young's Equation 2.8:

$$\gamma_{LV} \cdot \cos \theta_{con} = \gamma_{SV} - \gamma_{SL} \quad (2.8)$$

where θ_{con} is the contact angle, γ_{LV} is the surface tension between the liquid and vapour phase, γ_{SV} is the surface tension between the solid and vapour phase, and γ_{SL} is the surface tension between the solid and the liquid phase, as seen in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Schematic illustration of a liquid wetting a solid with contact angle, θ_{con} .

If $\theta > 90^\circ$, the liquid on the surface is considered to have low wettability, while if $\theta < 90^\circ$, the liquid is considered to have high wettability. The liquid is considered to be perfectly wetting if $\theta=0$.

The wetting properties of silicon on graphite is described in Section 2.4.1.3, and the wetting properties of ferrosilicon alloys on graphite is described in Section 2.4.5.1.

2.4 The Si-B-C-Fe system and its subsystems

The following section will provide an overview of the existing literature on the different subsystems in the Si-B-C-Fe system.

2.4.1 The Si-C binary system

The binary diagram of silicon and carbon is presented in Figure 2.4. The only stable phases in this system are silicon carbide (SiC), pure silicon and pure graphite. It is difficult to determine the exact values for the Si-C binary phase diagram due to the high temperatures, and therefore multiple liquidus temperatures are suggested. The most reliable investigation of the Si-C system was conducted by Dolloff (1962)^[21], where his thermal analysis results supported by metallographic and X-ray studies led to the determination of the eutectic temperature at 1404 ± 5 °C. In a similar manner, the peritectic transformation was determined to occur at 2545 ± 40 °C. Both transformations involve the intermediate compound, SiC, which has a stoichiometric composition at 50 at.% silicon and 50 at.% carbon. Below 50 at.% carbon the system will consist of solid or liquid silicon and solid SiC, and above 50 at.% the system will consist of solid graphite and SiC.

Figure 2.4: The binary system of silicon-carbon. The figure is taken from Hoel (1995)^[33].

SiC occurs in two modifications, cubic β -SiC (referred to as "low temperature" modification) and hexagonal α -SiC (referred to as "high temperature" modification). α -SiC

contains numerous polytypes with rhombohedral and hexagonal structures. The different polytypes are defined by how the SiC layers are stacked, while the thermodynamical differences are considered to be insignificant. β -SiC has a cubical crystal structure and is the most stable phase up to 1700 °C according to JANAF thermochemical tables, and the stability difference above 1700 °C is believed to be small. However, the main product in the Acheson process is α -SiC, which indicates that this structure is favoured at temperatures above 2000 °C^[24]. Important thermal properties of α -SiC and β -SiC are provided in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Thermal properties of α -SiC and β -SiC are provided in this table.^[36]

Property	Unit	α -SiC	β -SiC
Linear thermal expansion @ 300 K	K ⁻¹	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Thermal conductivity @ 300 K	W/(m·K)	490	360
Melting temperature	K	3103 ± 40	3103 ± 40
Density	g/cm ³	3.21	3.21

2.4.1.1 Solubility of carbon in the Si-C system

The solubility of carbon in liquid silicon in equilibrium with SiC is represented by the reaction:

The system consists of two components and two condensed phases. Gibbs phase rule is given by the equality:

$$F = C - P + 2, \quad (2.10)$$

where F is the number of degrees of freedom, C is the number of components and P is the number of phases in thermodynamic equilibrium with each other. At fixed pressure, the Si-C system has one degree of freedom according to Equation 2.10. If the amount of dissolved carbon in the silicon phase is measured at different temperatures, a relation for the carbon solubility as a function of temperature can then be obtained.

Multiple experimentalists have tried to establish such a solubility curve for the solubility

of carbon in silicon. However, there is a controversy regarding the determination of carbon content in the samples, which has resulted in some disagreement in the reported results. Figure 2.5 indicates that the works of Yanaba *et al.*(1997)^[75], Hall (1958)^[30], Ottem (1993)^[56], and Dalaker and Tangstad (2009)^[15] correspond well, while the works of Durand and Duby (1999)^[23], Oden and McCune (1987)^[54], and Scace and Slack (1959)^[60] deviate from this agreement.

Figure 2.5: Log-plot comparison with previously reported results. The lines are marked with their references. Dotted lines indicate extrapolations beyond the temperature regions in which the experiments were run. The figure is taken from Dalaker and Tangstad (2009)^[15].

Durand and Duby (1999)^[23] based their work on critical judgement of measurements from several different works. Their selection of solubility data was taken from Hall (1958)^[30], Dash(1959)^[16], and Kleykamp *et al.*(1993)^[41]. The three works were based on different experimental set-ups and analysing methods. As pointed out by Søyland (2004)^[67], Durand and Dolby obtained a value of 110 ppm mass by extrapolating the selected data, which is more than twice the value obtained by extrapolating Hall’s measurements alone.

Scace and Slack (1959)^[60] conducted a series of experiments using graphite and alumina crucibles in a graphite furnace. During the experiments using graphite crucibles, all carbon found in the alloy came from dissolution of the container. The carbon in solution

with the liquid silicon at high temperatures crystallised as SiC during cooling. They found that some silicon had penetrated into the crucible and that a layer of SiC had formed along the crucible. Olesinski and Abbaschian (1984)^[55] pointed out that this SiC layer would have functioned as a growth substrate for diffusion of carbon during quenching. The layer was removed before carbon analysis, which may have resulted in a underestimated carbon content. Scace and Slack (1959)^[60] argued that the loss was not significant from their reproducibility of experiments, an assumption disputed by the results of Yanaba *et al.*(1997)^[75], Hall (1958)^[30], Ottem (1993)^[56], and Dalaker and Tangstad (2009)^[15].

Oden and McCune (1987)^[54] conducted their experiments at high temperatures, between 1700-2150 °C, which makes the extrapolation of their results to the melting point uncertain. As pointed out by Dalaker and Tangstad (2009)^[15], they employed rapid quenching of the graphite crucibles followed by diamond grinding of the silicon ingot. Consequently, the issues regarding lost SiC in the work of Scace and Slack (1959)^[60] may also apply in this case.

Table 2.2 present a short summary the obtained results from the works mentioned above.

Table 2.2: Experimental and calculated values of carbon solubility in liquid silicon equilibrated with silicon carbide, adapted from Søyland (2004)^[67].

Investigators	Temperature [K]	Solub. at m.p./mass ppm
Yanaba <i>et al.</i> ^[75]	1723 - 1873	79
Oden and McCune ^[54]	1973 - 2423	5.7
Hall ^[30]	793 - 1998	41
Ottem ^[56]	1720 - 1950	56
Scace and Slack ^[60]	1833 - 2500	16
Durand and Duby ^[23]	1685 - 3101	110
Dalaker and Tangstad ^[15]	1687 - 1832	65

In experimental measurements performed with liquid silicon, interactions with the ambient atmosphere and the crucible may disturb the measurements. However, in experiments on solid solubility the measurements are conducted without crucibles and in vacuum conditions and the results may thus be less affected by experimental sources of error. Nozaki *et al.* (1970)^[53] investigated the behaviour of carbon in the fusion and crystallisation of silicon by the use of charged particle activation analysis. The carbon concentration just prior to the appearance of SiC was found to be 3 ppm (3.5 atoms/cm³) in all experiments,

regardless of the quantity of carbon painted on the rod. Søyland (2004)^[67] considered this to be a fairly accurate measurement and used an equilibrium distribution coefficient for carbon between 0.058 to 0.07 (literature values cited by Søyland (2004, Figure 2.2, p. 25))^[67]. This resulted in a liquid solubility ranging from 43 ppm mass to 52 ppm mass, which is in reasonable agreement with solubility values from Ottem (1993)^[56], Hall (1958)^[30], Yanaba *et al.* (1997)^[75], and Dalaker and Tangstad (2009)^[15].

2.4.1.1.1 Effect of boron on carbon solubility

The effect of boron on the carbon solubility in liquid silicon equilibrated with SiC has been investigated by Yanaba *et al.*(1998)^[76] in the temperature range 1450 °C to 1550 °C. They found that the solubility of carbon increased with increasing boron content in liquid silicon, as seen in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: The figure display the effect of boron content on the solubility of carbon in liquid silicon according to Yanaba *et al.*(1998)^[76].

Dalaker and Tangstad (2009) constructed an Arrhenius expression from their experimental data, which expresses the temperature dependence of the carbon solubility for different levels of boron. The best fit equations together with their results from experiments on pure silicon are plotted in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: The figure display the effect of boron content on the solubility of carbon in liquid silicon according to Dalaker and Tangstad (2009)^[15].

They found that the solubility of carbon was greater with additions of boron in all cases compared to the case of pure silicon. They also observed that the carbon concentration had increased with increasing boron content, apart from the case of 0.25%/50%. Thus, they found it reasonable to attempt to describe the carbon solubility as a function of both temperature and boron content, as presented in Figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8: The figure display the effect of boron content on the solubility of carbon in liquid silicon according to Dalaker and Tangstad (2009)^[15].

2.4.1.2 Effect of carbon on undercooling in silicon

SiC particles present in a system containing silicon will act as nucleation sites. To investigate how SiC affect the undercooling in silicon, experimentalists have measured the effect of impurities on pure silicon using the levitated droplet method. The benefit of this method is that the silicon is not in contact with a crucible, and contamination of foreign elements is avoided. This ensures that a controlled measurement on the effect of a particular element can be done. As discussed in the previous section, the reported values on the solubility of carbon in liquid silicon are deviating, while a better agreement of the carbon solubility for solid silicon is found at the melting temperature. The difference between the solubility in liquid and solid is significant, and the measured effect of carbon in the levitated droplet experiments is therefore likely due to nucleation on the precipitated SiC particles.

Reported values for the undercooling in pure silicon and silicon contaminated with carbon measured in levitated droplet experiments are presented in Table 2.3. For pure silicon the

reported nucleation undercooling is in the range of 300-420 K, while the addition of small amounts of carbon reduces the undercooling drastically. Beaudhuin *et al.* (2012)^[7] used a controlled flow of CH₄ gas to change the carbon concentration. When $1.8 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol gas was injected to the system, which corresponds to approximately 25 ppmw of carbon, the undercooling decreased from 300 K (pure silicon) to about 18 K. The undercooling was found to decrease further for higher injection levels of CH₄, to about 5 K at an injection level of $5.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.

Table 2.3: The table present reported undercooling values for pure silicon and silicon contaminated by carbon. The table is adapted from Undheim (2018)^[70].

Investigators	Si purity	Carbon [mass ppm]	Undercooling [K]
Li <i>et al.</i> ^[45]	5N	-	420
Inatomi <i>et al.</i> ^[35]	6N	-	320
Beaudhuin <i>et al.</i> ^[7]	6N	-	300
Beaudhuin <i>et al.</i> ^[7]	6N	25	12 ± 1.5
Beaudhuin <i>et al.</i> ^[7]	6N	70	5 ± 1

Significant precipitation of SiC was observed only for samples with high injection levels. The authors concluded that both precipitated SiC particles and interstitial carbon will affect the nucleation undercooling.

2.4.1.3 Wetting of carbon materials by liquid silicon

Several studies have been performed on the wettability of different carbon materials. Ciftja (2009)^[11], Yupko *et al.*(1977)^[77], and Li and Hausner (1995)^[46] have performed experiments investigating the wettability of carbon materials by liquid silicon. All these studies were performed using the sessile drop technique, which is used to characterise the surface tension by capillary action of a drop of liquid material on a solid substrate^[4].

Ciftja (2009)^[11] investigated the wetting of pure polycrystalline silicon on graphite substrates with different surface roughness. The experiments were conducted with a holding temperature of 1500 °C and in purified Ar (g) atmosphere. For smooth surfaces ($R_a < 0.1 \mu\text{m}$), the final contact angle for all graphite was found to be about 30°. The final contact angle was found to be decreasing with increasing surface roughness, and it could even reach 0° (full wetting). In that case, the silicon was completely absorbed by the graphite

material. The average surface roughness in which the final contact angle became zero was found to be different for different graphite materials. The cross-section of the samples were also investigated to analyse the penetration depth of silicon into the graphite. It was found that the penetration depth increased with the average pore diameter, as seen in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9: penetration depth of molten silicon versus the average pore diameter of graphite substrates. The figure is taken from Ciftja (2009)^[11].

The effect of surface roughness on the wetting of polycrystalline SiC by silicon was investigated by Yupko *et al.*(1976)^[77]. The wetting of rough surfaces was characterised by contact angle hysteresis, and because of this wetting was studied under both liquid inflow and outflow conditions. The inflow contact angle, θ_{in} , was found to be independent of surface roughness. The contact angle hysteresis in the wetting of polished base plates (with $R_z \approx 0.1 \mu\text{m}$) containing free silicon was found to be caused by the presence of a second phase. With increasing surface roughness, the hysteresis first grew up to $R_z \sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, and then remained unchanged for larger values.

It was considered that the base plates may have been pre-wetted by the free silicon located on the plates, which under the conditions in the experiments were in a liquid state. However, this possibility was rejected by the consideration that if silicon had spread over a pre-wetted surface, i.e. a surface coated by a silicon film, the measured values of the contact angle would have been close to zero. This was not observed in any

of the experiments, even at free silicon contents of more than 50 wt.%.

Li and Hausner (1995)^[46] investigated the wetting and penetration of commercial graphite materials by high purity silicon (99.999 %) by using the sessile drop technique. The time-dependent variation in the contact angle was determined at a constant temperature of 1430 °C in an Ar(g) atmosphere. Figure 2.10 illustrates the process of wetting of carbon by silicon. Melting starts at the contact points between silicon and the substrate once the melting point of silicon (1414 °C) is reached, as illustrated by (b) in Figure 2.10. During the melting, the silicon in liquid state starts to spread on the substrate, as illustrated by (c) in Figure 2.10. Complete melting was found to be achieved after 1.5 min. The contact angle, θ_{con} , was found to be relatively high at the moment of complete melting of the metal, but decreased rapidly with time. After 10 min, the contact angle had stabilised at relatively low values. The surface roughening of the graphite substrates was found to enhance the wetting, which correlates to the work done by Ciftja (2009).

Figure 2.10: Schematic representation of melting process of silicon and its spreading on the graphite substrate. (a) before melting; (b) start of melting; (c) during melting; (d) complete melting; (e) during spreading and (f) stabilisation. The figure is taken from Li and Hausner (1995)^[46].

Li and Hausner (1995) also investigated the vertical penetration depth of silicon into the graphite, denoted by H in Figure 2.11. A lateral penetration depth was also observed, denoted by D in Figure 2.11.

Figure 2.11: Schematic representation of a cross-section of the interface between silicon and graphite. θ is the contact angle, H is the vertical penetration depth, and D is the lateral penetration depth. The figure is taken from Li and Hausner (1995)^[46].

The vertical penetration depth, H , was found to be independent of the contact angles as seen in Figure 2.12, but increased with porosity (or pore size) of the graphite materials as seen in Table 2.4.

Figure 2.12: Vertical penetration depth, H , of silicon into the graphite as a function of the stationary contact angles. The figure is taken from Li and Hausner (1995)^[46].

Table 2.4: Mean values of the open porosity, pore size of various graphite materials, and the vertical penetration depth, H , (lower and upper limit values) of the materials by silicon. The experimental work is performed by Li and Hausner (1995)^[46].

Graphite	Porosity [%]	Pore size [μm]	Depth, H [mm]
N	17.77	0.06	0.85 - 1.05
UT86	17.72	0.07	0.80 - 0.95
EK77	18.65	0.10	0.95 - 1.25
CB620	17.02	0.05	0.40 - 0.75

The lateral penetration depth, D , was found to be increasing with decreasing contact angles, as seen in Figure 2.13. This suggests that the surface mobility of metal atoms on a substrate depends on the wetting and the interaction between the metal and the substrate.

Figure 2.13: Lateral penetration depth, D , of silicon into the graphite as a function of the stationary contact angles. The figure is taken from Li and Hausner (1995)^[46].

2.4.1.4 Formation of SiC during melting of silicon in a graphite crucible

Graphite materials may contain high porosity. As discussed in Section 2.3, Li and Hausner (1995)^[46] concluded that high porosity will result in an increased vertical penetration depth, H , of silicon into the graphite. This penetration is an important aspect that needs to be considered when applying graphite crucibles for phase change materials.

Zhou and Singh (1995)^[80] investigated the reaction kinetics and mechanisms in the Si-C reaction over a temperature range of 1430 °C to 1510°C. The reaction between liquid silicon with polycrystalline graphite showed that the liquid silicon physically penetrated into the pores of the graphite and reacted to form solid SiC. Most of the SiC was formed in an early stage of the reaction, and the growth rate of the SiC layer decreased in the latter period of the reaction due to the carbon being completely covered by the reaction-formed SiC layer. The reactants diffused through this layer to maintain the reaction, which resulted in growth of the SiC barrier layer as seen in Figure 2.14.

Figure 2.14: Microstructure of reaction formed SiC in the Si-C-Mo system at a) 1430 °C after 20 minutes and at b) 1430 °C after 180 minutes, as presented by Zhou and Singh (1995)^[80].

It was found that the variation in the average thickness of the reaction-formed SiC layer with reaction time in the temperature range of 1430 °C to 1510°C obeyed a fourth-power rate law with a correlation coefficient of above 0.9, as seen in Figure 2.15.

Figure 2.15: Thickness of the SiC layer as a function of the reaction time for Si-C reaction at 1430 °C, 1475 °C and 1510 °C. The figure is taken from Zhou and Singh (1995)^[80].

Einan (2012)^[24] investigated the formation of SiC particles and graphite in three different SiMn alloys in graphite crucibles at a temperature interval ranging from 1300 °C to 1610°C. The work was performed by exposing a SiMn alloy in a graphite crucible to multiple melting and solidification cycles. The results showed that the carbon content, present as graphite or SiC particles in the alloy, increased with the number of temperature cycles. Since the only source of carbon in the experiment was the graphite crucibles, the results suggested that the crucible was consumed with time.

Figure 2.16: Volume % of SiC and graphite. The rate of SiC/graphite formed at each cycle is decreasing with increasing amount of cycles. The figure is taken from Einan (2012)^[24].

The author conducted a series of experiments on the interaction of Si-B alloys in dense graphite crucibles during the summer and autumn of 2017^[28]^[29]. Three different types of experiments were performed on Si-B alloy with 8 at.% boron in dense graphite crucibles:

- The samples were heated through repeated temperature cycles in the liquidus state, between 1430 °C and 1550 °C.
- The samples were subjected to a set temperature for 10 minutes.
- The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 48 h.

The characterisation of the samples was mainly performed by light optical microscopy (LOM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and electron probe micro-analyser (EPMA). Sample 1, which was subjected to 1550 °C for 48 h, was investigated in SEM to characterise the phases formed in the experiments. Images were obtained from the inner bottom of the crucible, as seen in Figure 2.17. The different phases in the sample were investigated by EDS, and the results are indicated in the figure.

Figure 2.17: The image was obtained in SEM at the bottom of sample 1 from experiments conducted by the author (Des 2017)^[28]. The sample was investigated by EDS, and the phases that were found are indicated in the figure.

The results from experiments conducted by the author during the summer of 2017^[29] were compared to those obtained during the autumn of 2017^[28]. It was found that silicon had penetrated into the graphite to form SiC, and that a SiC barrier layer had formed along the interface between crucible and alloy for all samples. Mostly SiB₃ particles were found in the bulk. No direct correlation could be found between penetration depth and number of temperature cycles, as seen in Figure 2.18. However, the results indicated that silicon had penetrated into the graphite at an early stage of the process, with decreasing reaction rate with time, as presented by the grey line in the figure.

Figure 2.18: The graph expresses the results previously obtained by the author [28] [29]. The mean values of penetration depth of silicon into the graphite crucible in all three positions is plotted as a function of number of temperature cycles. The assumed mechanism of how SiC is formed is marked by the grey lines in the graph.

Similar results were observed for the formation of SiC barrier layer, where no correlation was found between the thickness of the layer and number of temperature cycles. A similar pattern for the reaction rate mechanism could also be observed for the barrier layer, as seen in Figure 2.19.

Figure 2.19: The graph expresses the results previously obtained by the author^{[28][29]}. The mean values of the SiC layer thickness formed at the interface between the alloy and the graphite crucible in all three positions is plotted as a function of number of temperature cycles. The assumed mechanism of how SiC is formed is marked by the grey lines in the graph.

The composition of the alloys after the experiments was calculated to be in the range of 7.16-9.09 at.% B. The results are thus considered to be representative for Si-B alloys with the eutectic composition of 8 at.% B.

The overall results indicated that the graphite crucibles would transform to even denser SiC with time, and the material was thus considered to be a stable container for eutectic Si-B alloy. A SiC barrier layer will be formed at the surface of the crucible, however, this was considered to not be detrimental to the main part of the phase change material over time. The overall results indicated that eutectic Si-B alloys contained in dense graphite crucibles are suitable for the application in LHTES system.

2.4.2 The Si-B binary system

The Si-B binary system includes six phases: Liquid, Si(diamond), β -B, SiB₃, SiB₆ and SiB_n (n = 14, 15, 40, etc.). The thermodynamic properties of Si-B alloys in solid and

liquid states are not very well known and only very few references exist on these compounds^[78]. Si-B alloys are mainly investigated due to their possible utilisation as high temperature materials, in which the most interesting reaction is the eutectic equilibrium. At this point a liquid during cooling solidifies under the formation of two solid phases:

The work performed by Olesinski and Abbaschian (1984)^[55] suggest that the eutectic reaction takes place at 1385 °C and 8 at.% boron, as shown in Figure 2.20.

Figure 2.20: The binary phase diagram of Si-B. The figure is taken from Olesinski and Abbaschian (1984)^[55].

2.4.3 The B-C binary system

The binary diagram of boron and carbon is presented in Figure 2.21. Boron carbide has a unique combination of properties that makes it suitable in a wide range of engineering applications. Due to its high melting point and thermal stability, B_4C is widely used in refractory applications and can potentially be used for novel electronic applications^[22].

Figure 2.21: The binary phase diagram of boron-carbon. The figure is taken from Landolt-Börnstein^[44].

The B-C phase diagram has been revised multiple times and the latest version is presented by Massalski (1990)^[48]. From Figure 2.21 it appears that B_4C melts congruently at 2731 K (2458 °C), and phase diagram calculations performed by Kasper (1996)^[39] show that the gas phase appears at 3900 K (3627 °C) and a carbon content of 55 at.%^[44].

2.4.4 The Si-B-C ternary system

The Si-B-C system has mainly been studied with respect to the sintering of ceramics. The understanding of mechanisms behind the sintering of SiC with boron and the sintering of boron carbide with silicon has been studied in particular^[14]. The stable intermediate compounds the Si-B-C system are silicon carbide (SiC), boron carbide ($B_{4+\delta}C$) and the silicon borides (SiB_3 , SiB_6 , and SiB_n). No ternary compounds exist. The ternary diagram of the system is presented in Figure 2.22.

Figure 2.22: A schematic phase diagram of the Si-B-C ternary system. The figure is taken from Dalaker (2009)^[14].

The system contains several equilibrium reactions, which are summarised in Table 2.5.

Table 2.5: List of equilibrium equations in the Si-B-C ternary system, adapted from Dalaker (2009)^[14]. Data is taken from Seifert and Aldinger^[62].

Temperature [°C]	Reaction
2385	$liquid + C \rightleftharpoons B_4C + SiC$
2005	$liquid + B \rightleftharpoons B_4C + SiB_n$
1850	$liquid + SiB_n \rightleftharpoons SiB_6 + B_4C$
1396	$liquid + SiC \rightleftharpoons B_4C + Si$
1384	$liquid \rightleftharpoons Si + SiB_6, B_4C$
1198	$Si + SiB_6 \rightleftharpoons SiB_3, B_4C$

2.4.5 The Fe-Si binary system

Silicon is an important alloying element in high-performance steels, such as electrical steel tailored to produce specific magnetic properties. To develop and produce such materials, phase diagrams and thermodynamic properties of the Fe-Si base alloys are helpful. The phase equilibria of this system has therefore been widely studied, and the experimental phase diagram proposed by Kubaschewski (1982)^[43] is presented in Figure 2.23.

Figure 2.23: The binary phase diagram of the iron-silicon system. The figure is taken from Kubaschewski (1982)^[43].

2.4.5.1 Wetting of graphite by ferrosilicon alloys

Silicon-rich ferroalloys and coke are two of the most important raw materials used in the scrap-iron process. The fundamental study of high temperature interaction between ferrosilicon and graphite is thus important to understand the interfacial reaction and wettability at the solid/liquid interface in this process.

The wettability of pure iron on graphite has been well investigated^{[34] [66] [74] [79]}. These studies showed that pure iron exhibited good wetting properties at temperatures between 1300-1500 °C under different atmospheres, with contact angles ranging from 0 to 66° as seen in Table 2.6. However, it was found that the wetting was highly affected by the

carbon content in the melt, in which the contact angle increased from $< 90^\circ$ to up to about 140° [66].

Table 2.6: Reported contact angle values of liquid iron on graphite, adapted from Rubio *et al.* (2009) [58].

Metal	Substrate	Atmosphere	T [°C]	θ [°]	Source
Molten iron	Graphite	Vacuum	1550	0	Humenik and Kingery (1954) [34]
Molten iron	Graphite	H ₂	1550	37	Humenik and Kingery (1954) [34]
Molten iron	Graphite	Helium	1550	51	Humenik and Kingery (1954) [34]
Pure iron	Graphite	Argon	1300	66	Sun <i>et al.</i> (1998) [66]
Pure iron	Graphite	Argon	1400	60	Sun <i>et al.</i> (1998) [66]
Pure iron	Graphite	Argon	1500	59	Sun <i>et al.</i> (1998) [66]
Pure iron	Graphite	Argon	1600	97-55-62	Wu and Sahjwalla (1998) [74]
Pure iron	Graphite	Argon	1600	64-38	Zhao and Sahjwalla (2003) [79]

Most wettability studies on silicon alloys has focused on the bonding properties of the Si-SiC system, while the dynamic wetting and its interdependence with interfacial reactions has not been investigated in depth. Rubio *et al.* (2006) [57] performed an in depth study on this topic, in which liquid ferrosilicon alloys containing 24.7% and 74% Si and pure silicon (98.5% Si) was investigated at 1550 °C using the sessile droplet method. Good wetting behaviour was observed for all ferrosilicon alloys on synthetic graphite and SiC. However, the contact angle decreased much more rapidly for the high-silicon ferroalloys compared to those with lower silicon content, as seen in Figure 2.24. Full wetting was observed within 90 s for high silicon alloys, while the dynamic wetting changed at a slower rate for FeSi 24.7%. In the low silicon alloys, the contact angle was found to be decreasing after 300 s, and remained steady at 70° .

(a) Dynamic wetting of Silicon 98.5% on synthetic graphite.

(b) Dynamic wetting of FeSi 74% on synthetic graphite.

(c) Dynamic wetting of FeSi 25% on synthetic graphite.

Figure 2.24: The figures show the dynamic wettability of silicon and two ferrosilicon alloys on synthetic graphite at 1550 °C, taken from Rubio *et al.* (2006)^[57].

The good wetting behaviour was found to be due to the formation of SiC as an interfacial product. Thus, the dynamic wetting appeared to be strongly dependent on the rate of SiC formation at the interface between ferrosilicon and graphite.

In studies performed by Rubio *et al.* (2006)^[57], the ferroalloys showed good wetting on SiC. However, the dynamic wetting behaviour was found to be different for high and low silicon alloys. The contact angle decreased down to 12° in 70 s for Si 98.5% and to 31° in 80 s for FeSi 74%. However, the decrease for FeSi 24.7% was found to be much slower, reaching 38° after 300 s as seen in Figure 2.25.

Figure 2.25: The figures show the dynamic wettability of silicon and two ferrosilicon alloys on SiC at 1550 °C, taken from Rubio *et al.* (2006)^[57].

XRD-analysis at the interface between ferrosilicon and graphite proved evidence regarding the formation of SiC during their interaction, which explains the reported differences on dynamic wetting. Peaks of SiC occurred after 30 and 60 s for Si 98.5% and FeSi 74%, respectively, while they appeared at 1800 s for FeSi 24.7%. This result indicates that the dynamic wetting is strongly related to the rate at which the interfacial reaction between FeSi and graphite occurs. The appearance of SiC as interfacial product also dictates the rate of carbon transfer.

2.4.5.2 Solubility of carbon in the Fe-Si system

Some studies has been performed on the solubility of carbon in ferrosilicon, but the results are found to be deviating. Ottem (1993)^[56] obtained thermodynamic data for the solubility of carbon in pure silicon, FeSi 75% and FeSi 65% at equilibrium with SiC. At 1550 °C, the carbon solubility in pure silicon was found to be 150-170 ppm, while the solubility in FeSi 75% and FeSi 65% were found to be 100–120 ppm and 70–75 ppm, respectively. The results showed a direct correlation between silicon content and carbon dissolved in the metal, in which higher silicon content gave higher carbon solubility as seen in Figure 2.26.

Figure 2.26: The solubility of carbon in silicon and ferrosilicon at 1550°C. The diagram is derived by Bakke (1995)^[6] on the basis of the work of Ottem (1993)^[56].

Chipman *et al.* (1951)^[10] reported the solubility data for the iron-rich part of the Fe-Si system. Data for ferrosilicon in equilibrium with graphite was presented in the temperature range between 1290-1960°C, and the composition range between 0-20% silicon. The result is shown in Figure 2.27.

Figure 2.27: The solubility of carbon in ferrosilicon in equilibrium with graphite at 1300°C, 1400°C, 1500°C, 1600°C, and 1700°C. The figure is taken from Chipman *et al.* (1952)^[10].

As seen in this figure, Chipman *et al.* found that higher silicon content gave lower carbon solubility, which is the opposite of the results obtained by Ottem. If these results are combined, the solubility of carbon appears to be decreasing with increasing silicon content up to approx. 50 wt.% silicon, while the solubility increase with increasing wt.% silicon at higher contents of silicon.

2.4.5.3 Activities in the Fe-Si system

Silicon has practically no solubility for foreign metals in its crystalline state, but forms stable silicides with most metals except for its neighbours in the periodic table. However, in its liquid state, silicon forms continuous solutions with most metals^[61]. Figure 2.28 presents the activities in the Fe-Si system, in which a negative deviation from ideal

behaviour (expressed by Raoult's law) can be observed for both silicon and iron. The activity of silicon is found to decrease with increasing amount of iron in this figure.

Figure 2.28: The figure presents the activities in the FeSi system, taken from Elliott (1963) [25].

2.4.6 The Fe-C binary system

The Fe-C phase diagram is fairly complex, and most research is conducted on the steel part of the diagram, up to around 7 wt.% carbon. The binary phase diagram of the system is presented in Figure 2.29. Steels are, in their simplest form, alloys of iron and carbon. At the low-carbon end of the metastable Fe-C phase diagram, ferrite (α -iron) dissolve at 0.028 wt.% C at 738 °C. Austenite (γ -iron) dissolve at 2.08 wt.% C at 1154 °C, and therefore has a considerably greater solubility of carbon compared with that of ferrite. The hardening of carbon steels, as well as many alloy steels, is based on this difference in the carbon solubility in ferrite and austenite. At the carbon-rich side of the metastable Fe-C phase diagram we find cementite (Fe_3C). δ -ferrite is found at the highest temperatures, but is of less interest in materials other than high alloyed steel. [12]

Figure 2.29: The binary phase diagram of the iron-carbon system^[71].

2.4.7 The Fe-B binary system

Boron is useful as an alloying element in many materials, including steel. Addition of boron to carbon and low alloyed steels at concentration levels of 0.0015 % to 0.0030 % will increase the hardness level through the enhancement of hardenability^[59].

The binary phase diagram of the iron-boron system is presented in Figure 2.30. This system is characterised by a small mutual solubility in the solid state, and the two compounds Fe_2B and FeB . Fe_2B is formed peritectically, while FeB melts congruently in a very narrow homogeneity range of about 1 at.%^[37].

Figure 2.30: The binary phase diagram of the iron-boron system. The figure is taken from Massalski (1996)^[49].

2.4.8 The Si-Fe-B ternary system

The Si-Fe-B ternary phase diagram is presented in Figure 2.31. The system contains eleven four-phase intersection points with liquid, in which the maximum temperature is at 2074.79 °C. When the temperature decreases to about 1380 °C, silicon starts to crystallise and SiB₆ is formed. At 1270 °C, SiB₆ is transformed to SiB₃. Fe₃Si₇ is generated at 1160 °C, and an eutectoid reaction takes place at 970 °C:

Figure 2.31: The ternary phase diagram of the silicon-iron-boron system. The phase diagram is calculated by Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, in FactSage using the FT Lite database.

3 Experimental

The purpose of the experimental work was to investigate the interaction between eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy and dense graphite crucibles. The alloy was exposed to high temperatures for 1 h, before temperature cycles around the eutectic point was initiated. The samples were analysed in LOM to investigate the degradation of the crucibles, and in EPMA and SEM to investigate the phases formed in the alloy. The wetting properties and volume expansion of the alloy at solidification was also investigated.

This section will first present several alloys that were considered to investigate for the application as phase change material in LHTES systems. Further, the raw materials and apparatus used in the experiments will be presented. The preparation of the master alloy and the embodiment of the wetting tests are then explained. Lastly, the experimental log and experimental method is presented.

3.1 Composition of the alloy

In LHTES systems the phase change material should release a large amount of energy during solidification, while the volume expansion should be low. To obtain an alloy with high fusion enthalpy it is reasonable to investigate elements with individual high fusion enthalpy, such as chromium, iron, nickel, and copper. The ternary phase diagrams for X-Si-B (Cr, Fe, Ni, Cu) alloys were investigated to find the eutectic compositions in the systems, and the ideal volume expansion and ideal fusion enthalpy was calculated for these alloys.

The ideal volume expansion was calculated by:

$$dV = \frac{V_s - V_l}{V_s} \quad (3.1)$$

where V_s is the average volume for the alloy in solid state, and V_l is the average volume for the alloy in the liquid state. The fusion enthalpy of the alloy was calculated by:

$$dH_{fus} = \frac{\sum H_{fus,x} \cdot V_{s,x}}{V_s} \quad (3.2)$$

where, $H_{fus,x}$ is the fusion enthalpy of each element, and $V_{s,x}$ is the volume of each element in solid state. The real fusion enthalpy of the alloys was calculated in FactSage using the FTlite and FactIPS database. The eutectic compositions with the highest fusion enthalpy and lowest volume expansion for each system are presented in Table 3.1. From these values, the most reasonable alloying elements were found to be chromium, iron, and nickel.

Table 3.1: Calculated values for volume expansion, ideal fusion enthalpy, and real fusion enthalpy for the most suited X-Si-B (Cr, Fe, Cu, Ni) alloys.

Composition [wt.%]	dV [cm^3/cm^3]	dH _{fus} ^{ideal} [kJ/cm^3]	dH _{fus} ^{real} [kJ/cm^3]
Si	0.11	4.09	4.09
Si _{0.97} B _{0.03}	0.10	4.30	4.42
Si _{0.43} B _{0.06} Cr _{0.52}	0.03	4.27	4.42
Si _{0.26} B _{0.09} Fe _{0.64}	-0.01	4.50	3.67
Si _{0.17} B _{0.0003} Cu _{0.83}	-0.02	2.84	0.08
Si _{0.08} B _{0.09} Ni _{0.83}	-0.08	4.81	3.05

The real enthalpy was calculated in FactSage at different temperatures around the four-phase intersection points (also called invariant points) for X-Si-B (Fe, Cr, Ni) alloys. This was done to make sure the reaction was in fact eutectic, and the results are presented in Figure 3.1, Figure 3.2, and Figure 3.3. From these figures, it can be observed that the reactions that take places at 1413.9 °C for Si_{0.43}B_{0.06}Cr_{0.52} and at 1156.9 °C for Si_{0.26}B_{0.09}Fe_{0.64} are eutectic, while the reaction which takes place at 927.6 °C for Si_{0.08}B_{0.09}Ni_{0.83} is most likely peritectic.

Figure 3.1: In this figure, the enthalpy for $\text{Si}_{0.43}\text{B}_{0.06}\text{Cr}_{0.52}$ at different temperatures is plotted. It can be observed that a eutectic reaction takes place at 1413.9 °C. The enthalpies were calculated in FactSage by Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, using the FT Lite database.

Figure 3.2: In this figure, the enthalpy for $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$ at different temperatures is plotted. It can be observed that a eutectic reaction takes place at 1156.9 °C. The enthalpies were calculated in FactSage by Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, using the FT Lite database.

Figure 3.3: In this figure, the enthalpy for $\text{Si}_{0.08}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Ni}_{0.83}$ at different temperatures is plotted. The reaction that takes place at $927.6\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is most likely peritectic. The enthalpies were calculated in FactSage by Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, using the FT Lite database.

Due to these calculations and observations, it was found that the most reasonable alloy to investigate in this thesis are $\text{Si}_{0.43}\text{B}_{0.06}\text{Cr}_{0.52}$ and $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$. However, due to time limitations it was decided to only investigate $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$.

The eutectic temperature for the $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$ alloy is at $1157\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and at this temperature the liquid will solidify into three phases:

$$\% \text{ Liq} = \% \text{ FeB} + \% \text{ B}_6\text{Si} + \% \text{ FeSi}, \quad (3.3)$$

as seen in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: The ternary phase diagram for Fe-Si-B system, calculated by Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, in FactSage using the FT Lite database. The point at which the eutectic reaction of the $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$ alloy takes place is marked by the red dot. The Alkemade lines are also marked by red lines in the figure.

The ternary phase diagram of the eutectic alloy at the eutectic temperature was calculated in FactSage by Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, as seen in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: The eutectic phase diagram for the $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$ alloy at 1157 °C. The diagram is calculated by Jian Meng Jiao, NTNU, in FactSage using the FT Lite database.

The amount of each phase was found by applying the Lever rule to this figure. The eutectic phase composition was found to be:

$$\% \text{Liq} = 24.31 \% \text{ FeB} + 7.78 \% \text{ B}_6\text{Si} + 68.13 \% \text{ FeSi} \quad (3.4)$$

3.2 Raw materials

Pure electronic grade silicon was provided by SINTEF in granule form, 99.9% pure boron powder was supplied by ZhongNuo Advanced Material Technology Co., Ltd., and 99% (metals basis) iron powder was supplied by Alfa Aesar. The same raw materials were used in all experiments. The impurities present in the boron powder and iron powder used in the experiments are listed in Table 3.2 and Table 3.3, respectively.

Table 3.2: The impurities present in the boron powder supplied by ZhongNuo Advanced Material Technology Co., Ltd. used in the experiments.

	Zr	Fe	Y	Al	Mg	Mn
Concentration [%]	6.29	1.28	0.23	0.066	0.012	0.0053

Table 3.3: The impurities present in the iron powder supplied by Alfa Aesar used in the experiments.

	O ₂	Mn	Si	P	C	S
Concentration [%]	0.35	0.18	0.09	0.016	0.01	0.01

3.3 Apparatus

The different types of apparatus used in the experimental work of this thesis are described in the following sections.

3.3.1 Crucibles

Four different crucibles were used during the experiments. A reference sample containing Si-B alloy with a eutectic composition of 96.76 wt.% silicon and 3.24 wt.% boron was made in a graphite crucible with an outer diameter of 40 mm. A master alloy was prepared in a 250 mL Al₂O₃ crucible. Prior to making the master alloy, an experiment was conducted on a 5 g sample in a 20 mL alumina crucible to investigate how the alloy would react with alumina. For the main experiments, dense graphite crucibles with an outer diameter of 22 mm were used as container for the alloy.

The alumina crucibles were delivered by CoorsTekTM, and the material data can be found in Table 3.4. The graphite crucibles were machined from a block of isostatically pressed graphite, and were delivered by Svenska Tanso AB. The porosity data of the graphite crucibles can be found in Table 3.5. The dimensions of all the crucibles can be found in Table 3.6 and in Figure 3.6.

Table 3.4: The alumina crucibles were delivered by CoorsTek™, and the material properties are provided in this table.

Property	Value	Unit
Purity	99.8	%
Temperature range	<1750	°C
Permeability	Gas tight	-
Water absorption	None	-

Table 3.5: The graphite crucibles were delivered by Svenska Tanso AB, and the porosity data is provided in this table.

Property	Value	Unit
Bulk density	1.90	Mg/m ³
Cumulative pore volume	0.052	m ³ /g
Open porosity	10	%
Radius of average open porosity	1.4	µm

Table 3.6: The table presents the dimensions of the four different crucibles used during the experiments in this thesis.

Material	Outer diameter [mm]	Wall thickness [mm]	Outer height [mm]	Bottom thickness [mm]
Al ₂ O ₃	59.00	2.00	105.00	3.00
Al ₂ O ₃	33.00	2.50	42.00	3.00
Graphite	40	4.22	42.87	4.06
Graphite	22	3.35	33.72	3.66

Figure 3.6: The figure presents cross sections, with dimensions, of the two types of alumina crucibles (left) and the two types of graphite crucibles (right) used in the experiments.

3.3.2 Induction furnace

The master alloy was prepared in an induction furnace, in which the heat is electrically applied by induction heating of metal. The advantage of this form of heating is that it's a clean, energy-efficient and well-controllable melting process compared to other methods of metal melting. The set-up of the induction furnace, "Blue furnace", is shown in Figure 3.7

Figure 3.7: Set-up of the induction furnace, "Blue Furnace", at NTNU in Trondheim, in which the master alloy was prepared.

3.3.3 Graphite tube furnace

The experiments were performed in a vertical graphite tube furnace. The heat is supplied by resistive heating, in which the passage of an electric current through graphite produces heat. The furnace is supplied with two different types of thermocouples, C-type and B-type. The software which controls the power supply to the furnace uses the C-type thermocouple that is located at the top of the furnace.

The set-up of the tube furnace, "TF2", is shown in Figure 3.8 and a schematic figure is included in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.8: Set-up of the resistance heated graphite tube furnace, "TF2", at NTNU in Trondheim.

Figure 3.9: Schematic figure of the graphite tube furnace, "TF2", at NTNU in Trondheim. This furnace was used in experiments on all other samples. The figure is based off a schematic drawing made by Bjørnstad^[8].

3.3.4 Thermogradient

The thermogradient in the graphite tube furnace was regularly investigated prior to the experiments. This was performed by setting the temperature to 1350 °C, with the side thermocouple (B-type) as controlling thermocouple. The temperature was measured at different positions in the furnace by moving the top thermocouple (C-type) up and down. The distance was measured from the top of the furnace to the bottom of the measuring thermocouple, in the range between 34 to 42 cm. The position was then plotted against the measured temperature to obtain the thermogradient in the furnace. The result is presented in Figure 3.10, and it can be observed that the temperature variation within the sample is less than 1-2 °C.

Figure 3.10: Investigation of the temperature gradient in the furncae. The temperature in the furnace is plotted against the distance from the bottom of the thermocouple.

The crucible should be placed in the warmest region of the furnace during the experiments. To mark the correct position for the crucible holder, the top thermocouple was placed at a distance of 42 cm measured from the top of the furnace. The crucible holder with

lid was then moved up in the furnace until the lid met the tip of the thermocouple, and the position was labeled on the crucible holder. Lastly, the thermocouple was moved up to 1 cm above the crucible holder lid (35 cm from the top of the furnace), to ensure no contact between the lid and the thermocouple during experiments. Due to the different positions, there will be a temperature difference of ~ 12 °C between the thermocouple and the alloy.

3.3.5 Cutting

The samples were cut with Struers Labotom-5 manual cut-off machine equipped with a diamond cut-off wheel (B0D25). All samples were first cut in half in vertical direction, as presented in Figure 3.11a and Figure 3.11b. Most of the samples could be removed from the crucible after the initial cutting as seen in Figure 3.11c, and this was done to be able to mold the samples easier in EpoFix. The samples that could not be removed from the crucibles were cut once more in horizontal direction to remove excess crucible, as presented in Figure 3.11d.

(a) The samples were cut vertically down the middle, as seen in the image.

(b) The samples after vertical cutting. Most of the alloys could be removed from the crucible after vertical cutting, and no further cutting was needed in this case.

(c) The alloy after being removed from the crucible.

(d) The samples that could not be removed from the crucible were also cut in horizontal direction to remove excess graphite.

Figure 3.11: The figures present how the samples were cut.

3.3.6 Mounting

All samples were mounted in EpoFix cold-setting embedding resin. 25 parts (per weight) of resin was thoroughly mixed with 3 parts (per weight) hardener for 90-120 s, and the samples were left for 12 h to harden.

3.3.7 Grinding and polishing

The samples were grinded and polished with ATM Saphir 550 electronically controlled grinding and polishing machine prior to analysis by LOM. A 220 grit Akasel diamond disc and an Allegro 9 grinding disc with 9 μm diamond suspension were used for grinding. 3 μm and 1 μm diamond suspensions on Akasel Daran and Akasel Napal polishing cloths were used for polishing.

(a) Sample 12 prior to mounting, grinding and polishing.

(b) Sample 12 after mounting, grinding and polishing.

Figure 3.12: Images show sample 12 prior to and after mounting, grinding and polishing.

3.3.8 Characterisation

The following sections present the different characterisation techniques used to analyse the samples in this thesis.

3.3.8.1 Microscopy

Microscopy is used to investigate objects and areas of objects that are not within the resolution range of the human eye. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) is a valuable instrument for characterisation of heterogeneous materials and surfaces in microscale. Several types of signals are formed in SEM, such as secondary electrons (SE), backscattered electrons (BSE), characteristic X-ray radiation, Auger electrons and photons with different angles. The most used signals in SEM are secondary electrons, backscattered electrons, and X-rays^[32]. These signals originate from different regions of the sample, as seen in Figure 3.13, hence different information can be obtained in SEM.

Figure 3.13: Interaction volumes by the secondary electrons, backscattered electrons, and x-rays^[32].

Secondary electrons originate from the surface or near-surface region of the sample, as seen in Figure 3.13. The emission of secondary electrons varies as a function of topography, and due to the excellent depth of field in SEM the images appear to be three dimensional.

Hence, secondary electrons are most often used to investigate the sample topography^[32].

Backscattered electrons originate from a wider region of the sample than secondary electrons, as seen in Figure 3.13. The signals occur due to elastic collisions between atoms and electrons, which result in a change of the electrons' trajectory. Larger atoms will scatter electrons more strongly than lighter elements, and thus create a stronger signal^[32]. This dependency between atomic numbers and number of backscattered electrons provides information on the sample's composition. Elements with higher Z -numbers appear as light phases in the image, while elements with lower Z -numbers appear darker. Different phases in the sample can thus easily be distinguished.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) will provide a semi-quantitative analysis involving identification of the different compounds present in the sample. All elements with $Z > 11$ (Na) can be detected by EDS, but not all instruments are equipped for detecting "lighter" elements with $Z > 5$ (B)^[32]. Thus, analysis of phases containing boron might not be accurate.

The samples were investigated with FESEM Hitachi SU-6600 at NTNU in Trondheim.

High conductivity is important to obtain precise results in SEM. Since EpoFix has non-conductive properties, the samples were wrapped in aluminium foil and a graphite tape was applied in contact with the surface as seen in Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14: The samples were wrapped in aluminium foil prior to SEM analysis. A graphite tape was used to assure contact with the foil and the sample.

The electron probe micro-analyser (EPMA) is primarily used for in-situ non-destructive chemical analysis of solid samples. It is fundamentally the same as a SEM, with the additional capability of chemical analysis. A solid material is bombarded by an accelerated and focused electron beam, which has sufficient energy to liberate both matter and energy from the sample. The electron-sample interactions mainly liberate heat, but they also yield both derivative electrons and x-rays. EPMA analysis of the phases present in sample 9, sample 10, sample 11 and sample 12 was performed by Senior Engineer Morten Peder Raanes, NTNU, in JXA-8500F Field Emission Electron Probe Microanalyzer.

Light Optical Microscopy (LOM) can be used to investigate the sample surface, such as distinguish different phases present. The inner surface of the crucibles were analysed with Leica MEF4M widefield inverted metallograph, to investigate if silicon had penetrated into the crucible to form SiC. Images were obtained from two positions at the left wall, the left corner, and the bottom the samples, as seen in Figure 3.15. The images were then analysed in iSolution. Note that the left wall and left corner of the samples will be located to the right in the image by the inverted microscope.

Figure 3.15: Images were obtained from two positions at the wall, the corner, and the bottom of the crucibles.

The principle of X-ray diffraction (XRD) is based on the reflection of a monochromatic X-ray beam that irradiates a crystal face, which is dependent on the lattice structure. The beam interacts with the sample with variable angle of incidence, and the reflexes are recorded together with the corresponding outgoing angles. These angles correspond with lattice spacing related to different plane sets, and are recorded in a diffractogram^[52]. To identify the samples, the diffractograms are compared with the patterns of known compounds. The composition of the phases present in a sample can thus be identified. XRD analysis of sample 11 and sample 12 was performed by Julian Richard Tolchard, SINTEF Industry.

3.3.8.2 Spectroscopy

Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) is an analytical technique used for elemental determinations. The ICP-MS analysis combines a high temperature inductively coupled plasma (ICP) source with a mass spectrometer. The ICP source converts

the atoms of the elements in the samples into ions, which are then separated and detected by the mass spectrometer^[13]. An ICP-MS analysis of the master alloy was performed by Senior Engineer Syverin Lierhagen, NTNU.

3.4 Preparation of Master alloy

A master alloy with a total weight of 100 g was prepared. The alloy consisted of 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si, and 9 wt.% B, and it was prepared in a 250 mL alumina crucible in an induction furnace. The alumina crucible was placed inside a larger crucible made of graphite. The graphite crucible was then placed on three graphite wool mats and wrapped in a layer of graphite wool and a layer of mica. A schematic drawing of the crucible set-up can be found in Figure 3.16. The sample was then placed in the furnace. The furnace was put in vacuum and then filled with Ar (g) three times to ensure no presence of oxygen. The sample was heated to 1750 °C and held at this temperature for 15 min to ensure complete melting.

Figure 3.16: The figure presents a schematic set-up of the making of the master alloy.

The alloy was crushed in a mortar into pieces with max. dimensions of 0.5 cm*0.5 cm. The pieces were then separated with a sample divider, which ensures representativeness of the sample.

3.5 Wetting properties

The wetting properties of the alloy on graphite substrate is an important aspect to investigate to decide if the alloy is suitable for the intended application. Research Scientist Sarina Bao, SINTEF Industry, performed several wetting tests on the alloy on both graphite and on alumina substrates. The wetting tests were video taped, and performed under different conditions.

In the second and third wetting test, an oxide layer appeared to be covering the sample surface. This had a negative effect on the melting, and it was therefore decided to submerge the samples in an acid bath prior to analysis. The acid bath contained one part hydrofluoric acid (HF), two parts ethanol, and five parts nitric acid (HNO₃). The samples were submerged for 10 s, rinsed with water and ethanol, and contained in ethanol until the tests were performed.

3.6 Experimental log

When a phase change material is applied in a LHTES system, the material will be exposed to repeated temperature cycles around the eutectic temperature. To investigate the behaviour of the alloy during operation, experiments with temperature intervals of $T_m \pm 20$ °C and $T_m \pm 100$ °C around the eutectic point were performed. Some challenges occurred during the first experiments, which resulted in several failed experiments. A log of all performed experiments are presented in Table 3.7.

Table 3.7: Log of all performed experiments, where M.A. denotes master alloy.

Sample	Date	Alloy	Crucible	# cycles	Temperature [°C]	Comments
1	23.01.2018	Si-B	Graphite	2 cycles	1414 ± 20	Failure
2	24.01.2018	Si-B	Graphite	2 cycles	1414 ± 20	Success
3	22.02.2018	Fe-Si-B	Graphite	2 cycles	1157 ± 20	Failure
4	22.02.2018	Fe-Si-B	Graphite	1 cycle	1157 ± 20	Failure
5	22.02.2018	Fe-Si-B	Graphite	1 cycle	1157 ± 20	Failure
6	23.02.2018	Fe-Si-B	Graphite	2 cycles	1157 ± 30	Failure
7	15.03.2018	Fe-Si-B	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Failure
8	21.03.2018	Fe-Si-B	Al ₂ O ₃	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
M.A.	05.04.2018	Fe-Si-B	Al ₂ O ₃	-	1750 (15 min)	Success
9	09.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
10	10.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
11	10.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	2 cycles	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
12	10.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
13	17.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	2 cycles	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
14	17.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	2 cycles	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
15	17.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 100	Success
16	20.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
17	20.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	2 cycles	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success
18	20.04.2018	M.A.	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 100	Success
19	11.05.2018	M.A.	Graphite	1 cycle	1550 (1h), 1157 ± 20	Success

The experiments were mainly performed with one and two temperature cycles, and graphic representations of the experiments are presented in Figure 3.17, Figure 3.18, Figure 3.19 and Figure 3.20.

Figure 3.17: The figure is a graphic representation of the experiments performed on the Si-B reference sample. The furnace was heated to 20 °C above the melting temperature before the sample was inserted. The temperature was held for 1 h, before cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C were initiated. One cycle is considered to be the interval from 1434 °C, down to 1394 °C, and back up to 1434 °C. There was a holding time of 10 min at the top and bottom of each interval. The sample was subjected to two temperature cycles.

Figure 3.18: The figure is a graphic representation of the experiments where the samples were subjected to temperature cycles around the eutectic point. The furnace was heated to 20 °C above the melting temperature before the sample was inserted. The temperature was held for 1 h, before cycles at $T_m \pm 20$ °C were initiated. One cycle is considered to be the interval from 1177 °C, down to 1137 °C, and back up to 1177 °C. There was a holding time of 10 min at the top and bottom of each interval. Experiments were performed with one and two cycles.

Figure 3.19: The figure is a graphic representation of the experiments where the samples were subjected to high temperature before cycles around the eutectic temperature was initiated. The furnace was heated to 1550 °C before the sample was inserted. The temperature was held for 1 h, before cycles at $T_m \pm 20$ °C were initiated. One cycle is considered to be the interval from 1177 °C, down to 1137 °C, and back up to 1177 °C. There was a holding time of 10 min at the top and bottom of each interval. Experiments were performed with one or two cycles.

Figure 3.20: The figure is a graphic representation of the experiments where the samples were subjected to high temperature before cycles around the eutectic temperature was initiated. The furnace was heated to 1550 °C before the sample was inserted. The temperature was held for 1 h, before cycles at $T_m \pm 100$ °C were initiated. One cycle is considered to be the interval from 1257 °C, down to 1057 °C, and back up to 1257 °C. There was a holding time of 10 min at the top and bottom of each interval. Experiments were performed with one cycle.

3.7 Method

All experiments were conducted in the resistance heated furnace "TF2" at NTNU (Trondheim). As mentioned in Section 3.3.4, there was a temperature difference of ~ 12 °C between the thermocouple and the alloy, which had to be accounted for during the experiments. $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$ has a melting temperature of 1157 °C, and the furnace was therefore programmed to run experiments at 1145 ± 20 °C and 1145 ± 100 °C.

A sample containing eutectic Si-B alloy was made as a reference sample. The sample was prepared by weighing out and thoroughly mixing 3.24 wt.% (8 at.%) of boron and 96.76 wt.% (92 at.%) silicon, and a 40 mm crucible was filled with ~ 20 g of powder. The experiment on this sample was run with two intervals between $T_m \pm 20$ °C to investigate if the crucible would be damaged during cycles around the eutectic temperature. If the crucible was damaged, the set-up of the experiment would have to be changed. During the first experiment, impurities from the graphite tube inside the furnace had reacted with the sample, and the experiment was thus considered unsuccessful. The furnace was disassembled and cleaned thoroughly and a graphite lid was added to the crucible holder. The second experiment was considered successful and the experimental set-up could be used for further experiments.

Results from previous experiments indicated that all boron in the Si-B alloy dissolved rapidly during the experiments, hence it was initially decided to not produce a pre-melted master alloy for the Fe-Si-B alloy either. For the initial experiments, the alloy was prepared by thoroughly mixing 0.26 wt.% Si, 0.09 wt.% B, and 0.64 wt.% Fe. Three experiments were conducted on $\text{Si}_{0.26}\text{B}_{0.09}\text{Fe}_{0.64}$, in which the raw materials did not melt down to form an alloy. The temperature interval was increased to $T \pm 30$ °C in a fourth experiment, but this had no effect on the melting.

To investigate any possible errors with the thermocouples in the furnace, a calibration was performed. This was done by conducting an experiment on pure copper, which has a melting temperature of 1085 °C. The copper sample was exposed to 1115 °C for 10 minutes, and the sample had melted completely. This indicates that the thermocouples were well functioning.

An experiment was conducted in which the raw materials were divided into two layers in the crucible, with iron in the bottom, and silicon and boron mixed at the top. This sample was exposed to 1550 °C for 1 h, before temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C was initiated. The sample had melted down, but significant amounts of carbides had formed in the upper part of the sample, which indicates that the components did not mix well during melting.

Due to the challenges of forming an alloy, it was decided to prepare a pre-melted master alloy before conducting any further experiments. Mixing during melting appeared to be a problem in the previous experiments, and it was therefore decided to prepare the master alloy in an induction heated furnace. An alumina crucible was used instead of graphite to avoid formation of carbides, and an experiment on the reactivity between alumina and Fe-Si-B alloy was conducted prior to preparing the master alloy. The reactivity between the alloy and alumina was found to be low, and a master alloy with a total weight of 100 g was prepared.

The following experiments were performed on approx. 6 g of master alloy in graphite crucibles. The samples were first subjected to 1550 °C for 1 h to ensure complete melting of the alloy, before temperature intervals of $T_m \pm 20$ °C and $T_m \pm 100$ °C were initiated. Experiments were mainly performed with one and two temperature cycles. One experiment was conducted with 12 g of master alloy to investigate the effect of volume expansion of the alloy on the crucible during solidification.

The log of the performed experiments is presented in Table 3.7 in Section 3.6. Graphic representations of the experiments are presented in Figure 3.17, Figure 3.19, and Figure 3.20 in Section 3.6.

After the experiments, the cylindrical containers were cut and the samples and crucibles were mounted, grinded, and polished as described earlier in this section. After polishing the samples were cleaned in ethanol and submerged in an ultra sound bath for 5 min. This was done to remove all water form the samples to prevent corrosion.

The composition of the master alloy was determined by ICP-MS analysis performed by Senior Engineer Syverin Lierhagen, NTNU. The elements present in the phases in sample

9, sample 10, sample 11, and sample 12 were investigated in EPMA by Senior Engineer Morten Peder Raanes, NTNU. The internal surface of the alloys were mainly investigated by SEM to investigate the distribution of phases in the samples. The internal surface of the crucibles were mainly investigated in LOM, to investigate if silicon had penetrated into the crucible and formed SiC. Research Scientist Julian Richard Tolchard, SINTEF Industry, attempted to determine the composition of the phases by XRD analysis. However, the crystal growth in the samples made them difficult to analyse, and the results from the XRD-analysis are thus only included in Appendix A. The wetting properties of the alloy on graphite and alumina substrates were investigated by Research Scientist Sarina Bao, SINTEF Industry.

4 Results

The results from the performed experiments will be presented in this section.

First, the result from the ICP-MS analysis is presented to determine the composition of the master alloy. Next, the results from EPMA and SEM are presented, in which the different phases formed during the experiments were determined. Further, the images obtained in LOM and results from the wetting tests are presented, in which the reactivity between the alloy and the crucibles were investigated. The last section highlights the challenges that occurred during the experiments.

4.1 ICP-MS

An ICP-MS analysis was conducted by Senior Engineer Syverin Lierhagen, NTNU, to determine the composition of the master alloy. Both the detected and normalised wt.% of silicon, boron, and iron, in addition to the ideal composition of the alloy, are listed in Table 4.1. The detected values are well within 3% deviation of the ideal composition.

Table 4.1: Quantitative results of the ICP-MS analysis performed on the master alloy by Senior Engineer Syverin Lierhagen, NTNU. The ideal composition of the alloy and normalised result are also included.

	wt.% Si	wt.% B	wt.% Fe
Ideal composition	26.46	9.38	64.16
Results	27.87	9.54	66.45
RSD [%]	4.2	1.3	2.6
Normalised results	26.73	9.15	63.72

Aluminium and manganese were the only two trace elements of highest concentration found in the alloy. However, as seen in Table 4.2, the concentration of these elements was still very small. The aluminium content might originate from the alumina crucible used during making of the master alloy. The manganese content originated most likely from impurities in the iron powder, as presented in Table 3.3 in Section 3.2.

Table 4.2: Quantitative result of trace elements found in the master alloy by ICP-MS performed by Syverin Lierhagen.

	wt.% Al	wt.% Mn
Results	0.1817	0.2284
RSD [%]	3.3	5.0
Normalised results	0.1743	0.219

4.2 EPMA

It is important to determine the phase composition of the samples to determine if the intended eutectic composition is reached. Also, eutectic Fe-Si-B is a system that has not been widely researched, and it is thus important to determine how the phases are precipitated at high temperatures to gain knowledge about the system.

Sample 9, sample 10, sample 11, and sample 12 were characterised in EPMA by Senior Engineer Morten Peder Raanes, NTNU. The samples were carbon sputtered prior to analysis, to ensure sufficient conductivity of the samples. This resulted in detection of a carbon content of at least 5.64-16.86 at.% in all analyses, which is taken into account when the phase compositions are identified.

As mentioned in Section 3.1, a phase composition of 24.31 % FeB, 7.78 % SiB₆, and 68.13 % FeSi is expected in the alloy.

In the experiments previously performed by the author (2017)^{[28][29]} large amounts of SiC was found along the edge of the samples, in which silicon had reacted with the crucible. Due to the lower silicon content of the Fe-Si-B alloy, less SiC particles are expected to be found in the current alloy.

According to an internal report produced by Jian Meng Jiao (to be published in 2018)^[38], B₄C particles were found in Si-B alloys with boron content of 5 wt.% and higher. Due to the low boron content of 3.24 wt.% in the previous experiments on Si-B alloy, no B₄C particles were detected in these samples. However, the boron content in the current alloy is much higher (9.38 wt.%), and it is thus expected to find some B₄C particles near the edge of the samples.

The top, centre and bottom of each sample were investigated and analysed.

Sample 9 was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C. The results from the analysis conducted from this sample is included in the figures and tables in the next pages.

The image obtained from the top of sample 9 is included in Figure 4.1, in which nine points were investigated. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.3.

Figure 4.1: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 9. Nine points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.3: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the top of sample 9.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	39.76	10.27	40.47	8.94	0.4892	0.049	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
2	39.014	12.03	39.77	8.68	0.46	0.034	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
3	38.46	13.06	39.01	8.88	0.52	0.08	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
4	48.65	0.00	0.55	50.19	0.56	0.04	SiC
5	49.14	0.00	0.61	49.91	0.27	0.07	SiC
6	48.97	0.00	0.60	50.10	0.28	0.04	SiC
7	2.30	84.91	0.41	7.91	0.08	4.40	SiB ₆
8	2.36	85.01	0.42	7.64	0.08	4.47	SiB ₆
9	2.22	85.26	0.32	7.51	0.11	4.58	SiB ₆

^{*)} Not found in the phase diagram.

Some SiC particles were identified in the top part of sample 9, as expected. However, no B₄C particles were found in this area. The darkest grey phase was identified as SiB₆ particles. The matrix was identified as the three-phase compound, Si₄BFe₄, which was not found in the phase diagram.

The image obtained from the centre of sample 9 is included in Figure 4.2, in which nine points were investigated. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.4.

Figure 4.2: EPMA analysis of the centre of sample 9. Nine points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.4: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the centre of sample 9.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	38.85	10.96	40.72	8.89	0.56	0.03	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
2	0.09	49.35	43.48	6.61	0.43	0.04	FeB
3	0.40	49.06	43.55	6.63	0.35	0.00	FeB
4	18.50	53.07	19.88	8.02	0.45	0.08	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
5	18.16	53.73	19.57	7.99	0.45	0.10	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
6	19.56	50.82	20.60	8.31	0.64	0.07	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
7	1.52	85.55	0.38	7.55	0.14	4.87	SiB ₆
8	2.02	85.03	0.46	7.53	0.11	4.84	SiB ₆
9	2.38	85.26	0.44	7.46	0.03	4.43	SiB ₆

^{*)} Not found in the phase diagram.

The dark phase in this area was identified as SiB₆, which corresponds to the analysis of the dark phase in the top of the sample. The lighter grey area was identified as Si₂B₅Fe₂, which is the second three-phase component not identified in the phase diagram. FeB

and Si_4BFe_4 were found as matrices in this area, which indicates that these phases were precipitated prior to the other phases.

The image obtained at the bottom of sample 9 is included in Figure 4.3. Nine points were analysed at the bottom of this sample, and the result from the analysis is presented in Table 4.5.

Figure 4.3: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 9. Nine points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.5: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the bottom of sample 9.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	0.13	48.68	43.77	7.03	0.36	0.02	FeB
2	0.07	49.39	43.46	6.68	0.40	0.02	FeB
3	0.13	49.56	43.35	6.58	0.38	0.00	FeB
4	48.59	0.00	0.35	50.72	0.30	0.03	SiC
5	48.37	0.00	0.26	50.95	0.37	0.05	SiC
6	47.69	0.00	0.50	51.43	0.35	0.03	SiC
7	9.40	78.03	0.17	11.11	0.20	1.09	SiB ₆
8	9.39	77.97	0.22	10.96	0.15	1.31	SiB ₆
9	9.49	82.06	0.43	7.13	0.11	0.77	SiB ₆

**) Not found in the phase diagram.*

SiC particles were identified at the very bottom as expected, while no B₄C particles were detected in this area either. The darkest grey phase was identified as SiB₆ particles, and

FeB was identified as the matrix. The three-component phases, $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$ and Si_4BFe_4 , were not found in this area.

Sample 10 was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C. The results from the analysis conducted from this sample is included in the figures and tables in the next pages.

The image obtained from the top of sample 10 is included in Figure 4.4, in which nine points were investigated. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.6.

Figure 4.4: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 10. Nine points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.6: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the top of sample 10.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	38.03	12.47	40.03	8.97	0.48	0.02	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
2	37.58	12.64	39.83	9.31	0.62	0.04	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
3	37.43	12.15	40.07	9.66	0.68	0.02	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
4	46.23	0.00	0.46	52.97	0.33	0.01	SiC
5	44.06	0.00	0.44	55.11	0.38	0.01	SiC
6	47.94	0.00	0.60	51.06	0.35	0.04	SiC
7	1.16	78.20	0.50	18.85	0.20	1.08	B ₄ C
8	8.87	80.47	0.62	8.74	0.19	1.11	SiB ₆
9	2.15	81.92	1.43	13.61	0.13	0.76	SiB ₆

*) Not found in the phase diagram.

As for sample 9, SiC particles were identified at the edge of sample 10 as expected. However, some B₄C particles were detected in this area. In correspondence with the analysis of sample 9, the dark grey phase was found to be SiB₆. Only Si₄BFe₄ was found

as matrix. Neither $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$ nor FeB were identified in this area.

The image obtained from the centre of sample 10 is included in Figure 4.5, in which nine points were investigated. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.7.

Figure 4.5: EPMA analysis of the centre of sample 10. Nine points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.7: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the centre of sample 10.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	37.69	9.84	42.81	9.19	0.45	0.02	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
2	38.03	9.38	42.73	9.32	0.54	0.00	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
3	37.73	9.86	42.34	9.60	0.44	0.03	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
4	19.23	50.22	21.49	8.46	0.47	0.13	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
5	19.24	50.48	21.23	8.30	0.69	0.06	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
6	19.30	50.10	21.59	8.38	0.56	0.07	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
7	7.08	82.37	0.34	8.08	0.16	1.97	SiB ₆
8	6.72	82.96	0.36	7.89	0.13	1.95	SiB ₆
9	10.61	78.33	3.68	6.38	0.12	0.88	SiB ₆

^{*)} Not found in the phase diagram.

As for sample 9, no SiC or B₄C particles were detected in the centre of the sample. Once again, the dark grey phase was found to be SiB₆ and the lighter grey phase was identified as Si₂B₅Fe₂. Only Si₄BFe₄ was found as matrix, while no FeB was detected in this area.

The image obtained at the bottom of sample 10 is included in Figure 4.6. Twelve points were analysed at the bottom of this sample, and the result is presented in Table 4.8.

Figure 4.6: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 10. Twelve points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.8: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the bottom of sample 10.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	38.25	9.38	42.47	9.44	0.45	0.01	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
2	0.20	47.23	44.48	7.53	0.53	0.03	FeB
3	0.17	46.24	44.47	8.20	0.88	0.04	FeB
4	18.87	50.46	21.33	8.85	0.43	0.07	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
5	18.73	50.00	20.57	10.13	0.50	0.07	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
6	18.72	50.70	20.60	9.46	0.47	0.06	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
7	48.03	0.00	0.62	50.98	0.33	0.04	SiC
8	48.20	0.00	0.50	50.73	0.52	0.05	SiC
9	46.66	0.00	0.40	52.48	0.45	0.01	SiC
10	9.56	78.43	0.36	10.09	0.16	1.41	SiB ₆
11	9.61	79.91	0.39	8.85	0.24	1.00	SiB ₆
12	8.31	79.50	0.41	9.01	0.56	2.20	SiB ₆

*) Not found in the phase diagram.

As for sample 9, SiC particles were identified at the very bottom of the sample, while no B₄C particles were detected in this area. The darkest grey phase was identified as SiB₆ particles, while the lighter grey area was identified as Si₂B₅Fe₂. Both FeB and Si₄BFe₄ were once again found as matrix.

Sample 11 was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C. The results from the analysis conducted from this sample is included in the figures and tables in the next pages.

The image obtained from the top of sample 11 is included in Figure 4.7, in which twelve points were investigated. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.9.

Figure 4.7: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 11. Twelve points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.9: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the top of sample 11.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	37.23	12.69	40.69	8.87	0.45	0.06	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
2	33.89	11.57	36.86	16.86	0.75	0.07	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
3	37.57	11.34	40.60	9.88	0.46	0.14	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
4	18.13	52.66	20.06	8.50	0.40	0.25	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
5	18.17	46.18	20.17	13.38	1.92	0.19	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
6	18.76	52.00	20.73	7.96	0.50	0.05	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
7	48.71	0.00	0.66	50.28	0.29	0.06	SiC
8	47.52	0.00	0.71	51.23	0.53	0.00	SiC
9	48.92	0.00	0.67	50.14	0.18	0.09	SiC
10	0.93	79.48	0.29	17.36	0.06	1.87	B ₄ C
11	0.72	79.37	0.24	17.71	0.09	1.87	B ₄ C
12	0.44	78.89	0.28	18.33	0.07	2.00	B ₄ C

*) Not found in the phase diagram.

As for sample 9 and sample 10, SiC particles were identified at the top of sample 11. B₄C particles were also identified in this area, close to the SiC particles. Si₂B₅Fe₂ was found as a light grey phase, and Si₄BFe₄ was found as matrix. No SiB₆ or FeB were identified in this area.

The image obtained from the centre of sample 11 is included in Figure 4.8, in which nine points were investigated. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.10.

Figure 4.8: EPMA analysis of the centre of sample 11. Nine points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.10: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the centre of sample 11.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	0.17	48.01	44.55	6.73	0.49	0.05	FeB
2	0.15	42.55	44.88	10.18	2.21	0.03	FeB
3	0.16	48.09	44.61	6.82	0.30	0.01	FeB
4	16.46	52.59	22.08	8.24	0.57	0.06	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
5	16.68	52.24	21.88	8.57	0.59	0.04	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
6	16.68	52.94	21.71	8.18	0.45	0.04	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
7	5.37	82.61	0.48	9.33	0.11	2.09	B _{4+δ} C
8	1.20	84.87	0.50	8.03	0.07	5.32	B _{4+δ} C
9	4.07	81.44	3.57	6.35	0.12	4.45	B _{4+δ} C

*) Not found in the phase diagram.

As for sample 9 and sample 10, no SiC particles were detected in this area. The lighter grey phase was identified as Si₂B₅Fe₂. Only FeB was found as matrix, while no Si₄BFe₄ was detected. As seen in the phase diagram of the B-C system in Section 2.4.3, B₄C can

have a boron content in the range of 80-93 at.%. The dark phase in this area was thus found to be $B_{4+\delta}C$. The $B_{4+\delta}C$ contained a slightly higher concentration of Al compared to the other phases.

The image obtained at the bottom of sample 11 is included in Figure 4.9. Twelve points were analysed at the bottom of this sample, and the result is presented in Table 4.11.

Figure 4.9: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 11. Twelve points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.11: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the bottom of sample 11.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	0.25	47.35	45.12	6.79	0.47	0.02	FeB
2	34.31	9.53	45.94	9.46	0.77	0.00	Si ₄ BFe ₄ ^{*)}
3	0.29	47.49	44.68	6.99	0.52	0.03	FeB
4	15.94	48.66	23.83	10.89	0.60	0.08	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
5	14.73	51.99	23.53	9.13	0.60	0.03	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
6	13.23	51.33	26.02	8.78	0.57	0.07	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ ^{*)}
7	49.27	0.00	0.29	49.94	0.47	0.03	SiC
8	49.07	0.00	0.45	50.16	0.31	0.02	SiC
9	48.96	0.00	0.44	50.31	0.28	0.01	SiC
10	10.28	80.40	0.35	7.58	0.09	1.30	SiB ₆
11	9.98	80.67	0.36	7.51	0.10	1.38	SiB ₆
12	10.23	80.41	0.35	7.57	0.11	1.33	SiB ₆

^{*)}Not found in the phase diagram.

As for sample 9, SiC particles were identified at the very bottom, while no B₄C particles were detected in this area. The darkest grey phase was identified as SiB₆ particles, while the lighter grey area was identified as Si₂B₅Fe₂. Both FeB and Si₄BFe₄ were once again found as matrices.

Sample 12 was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C. The results from the analysis conducted from this sample is included in the figures and tables in the next pages.

The image obtained from the top of sample 12 is included in Figure 4.10, in which twelve points were investigated. The result is presented in Table 4.12.

Figure 4.10: EPMA analysis of the top of sample 12. Twelve points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.12: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the top of sample 12.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	40.22	9.04	41.71	8.49	0.54	0.00	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
2	40.55	8.43	41.97	8.63	0.42	0.00	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
3	39.99	8.83	41.97	8.71	0.47	0.03	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
4	18.71	53.68	19.48	7.52	0.55	0.05	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
5	18.66	53.84	19.38	7.62	0.44	0.06	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
6	18.81	53.67	19.51	7.37	0.50	0.13	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
7	49.24	0.00	0.63	49.89	0.22	0.02	SiC
8	49.19	0.00	0.69	49.89	0.19	0.04	SiC
9	48.93	0.00	0.70	50.12	0.24	0.01	SiC
10	0.60	79.03	0.23	18.08	0.15	1.91	B ₄ C
11	2.33	81.60	1.49	13.42	0.07	1.10	B ₄ C
12	0.69	78.10	0.26	19.18	0.13	1.64	B ₄ C

*) Not found in the phase diagram.

In correspondence with the analysis of sample 11, both SiC particles and B₄C were identified at the top of sample 12. Si₂B₅Fe₂ was found as a light grey phase, while only Si₄BFe₄ was found as matrix. No SiB₆ or FeB were identified in this area.

The image obtained from the centre of sample 12 is included in Figure 4.11, in which nine points were investigated. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 4.13.

Figure 4.11: EPMA analysis of the centre of sample 12. Nine points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.13: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the centre of sample 12.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	40.44	8.71	41.63	8.82	0.39	0.02	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
2	40.03	9.57	41.01	8.88	0.47	0.04	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
3	40.91	7.73	41.91	9.05	0.39	0.00	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
4	18.43	54.09	19.21	7.82	0.42	0.03	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
5	18.47	53.96	19.25	7.80	0.47	0.04	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
6	18.47	54.02	19.32	7.69	0.45	0.05	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
7	0.72	85.15	0.73	7.79	0.12	5.49	B _{4+δ} C
8	0.95	86.24	0.39	7.03	0.07	5.31	B _{4+δ} C
9	2.39	85.40	1.85	5.99	0.09	4.27	B _{4+δ} C

*) Not found in the phase diagram.

As for the previous samples, no SiC particles were detected in the centre of the sample. The lighter grey phase was identified as Si₂B₅Fe₂. As apposed to sample 11, only Si₄BFe₄ was found as matrix, while no FeB was found. The dark phase in this area was found to

be $B_{4+\delta}C$ particles. Once again, the $B_{4+\delta}C$ contained a slightly higher concentration of Al compared to the other phases.

The image obtained at the bottom of sample 12 is included in Figure 4.12. Twelve points were analysed at the bottom of this sample, and the result is presented in Table 4.14.

Figure 4.12: EPMA analysis of the bottom of sample 12. Twelve points were investigated in this area.

Table 4.14: Quantitative result of the EPMA analysis conducted on the bottom of sample 12.

Analysis	at.% Si	at.% B	at.% Fe	at.% C	at.% O	at.% Al	Compound
1	39.77	9.35	40.66	9.77	0.44	0.01	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
2	39.52	9.65	40.77	9.55	0.48	0.04	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
3	40.67	7.90	41.79	9.10	0.52	0.03	Si ₄ BFe ₄ *)
4	18.88	52.59	19.66	8.28	0.49	0.10	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
5	18.69	53.07	19.32	8.31	0.48	0.13	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
6	19.05	52.70	19.74	7.91	0.44	0.17	Si ₂ B ₅ Fe ₂ *)
7	49.05	0.00	0.62	50.00	0.29	0.03	SiC
8	48.81	0.00	0.59	50.26	0.31	0.03	SiC
9	48.32	0.00	0.60	50.69	0.35	0.04	SiC
10	2.88	84.56	2.42	5.64	0.08	4.41	B _{4+δ} C
11	1.77	85.52	1.21	6.58	0.09	4.83	B _{4+δ} C
12	1.71	85.42	1.47	6.49	0.08	4.84	B _{4+δ} C

*) Not found in the phase diagram.

As for the other samples, SiC particles were identified at the very bottom. Except for the SiC particles, the phases detected at the bottom of the sample is similar to those detected in the centre. This include $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$ detected as a light grey phase, Si_4BFe_4 detected as a matrix, and $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ detected as a dark grey phase. As for the other $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ phases detected, a slightly higher concentration of Al was found.

4.2.1 X-ray analysis

Senior Engineer Morten Peder Raanes, NTNU, also conducted X-ray analyses of sample 10 and sample 11. An error occurred during the analyses, in which carbon was not measured. The carbon analysis is therefore not included in the figures.

The analysis conducted at the top of sample 10 is presented in Figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13: X-ray analysis conducted at the top of sample 10.

The analysis correspond well to the point analysis conducted in the same area, in which silicon is found in the matrix and SiC particles are located close to the edge. Boron was detected in phases found to be B_4C and SiB_6 , in which the signal is stronger from the SiB_6 phases than the B_4C phases. One area in the matrix appear to only contain iron, which does not correspond to the point analyses conducted in any of the areas in sample 10. It appears like the little amount of aluminium that was detected in the ICP-MS analysis has been evenly distributed in the sample, but with slightly higher concentrations in the SiB_6 phase.

The analysis conducted at the centre of sample 10 is presented in Figure 4.14.

Figure 4.14: X-ray analysis conducted at the centre of sample 10.

The analysis correspond well to the point analysis conducted in the same area, in which silicon and iron is found in the matrix. Boron was detected in phase found to be SiB_6 . Aluminium was once again found to be evenly distributed in the sample, but with slightly higher concentrations in the SiB_6 phase.

The analysis conducted at the bottom of sample 10 is presented in Figure 4.15.

Figure 4.15: X-ray analysis conducted at the bottom of sample 10.

There is one area close to the bottom in which only iron is detected, while Si_4BFe_4 was detected in the point analysis. A part in the top area that was found to be FeB in the point analysis, while the X-ray analysis only shows silicon in this area. There is a stronger signal for silicon in some phases at the bottom, which was found to be SiC in the point analysis. However, as previously pointed out, no carbon was detected in these areas. Aluminium was once again found to be evenly distributed in the sample, but with slightly higher concentrations in the SiB_6 phase.

The analysis conducted at the top of sample 11 is presented in Figure 4.16.

Figure 4.16: X-ray analysis conducted at the top of sample 11.

The analysis correspond well to the point analysis conducted in the same area, in which silicon is found in the matrix. SiC particles were located close to the edge. Boron was detected in phases found to be B_4C . Once again, one area in the matrix appear to only contain iron, which does not correspond to the point analyses conducted in any of the areas in sample 11 either. It appears like the little amount of aluminium that was detected in the ICP-MS analysis has been evenly distributed in the sample, but with slightly higher concentrations in the B_4C phase.

The analysis conducted at the centre of sample 11 is presented in Figure 4.17.

Figure 4.17: X-ray analysis conducted at the centre of sample 11.

The matrix found to be FeB in the point analysis show little concentration of boron in the X-ray analysis. The other areas correspond well to the point analysis. Aluminium was once again found to be evenly distributed in the sample, but with slightly higher concentrations in the $B_{4+\delta}C$ phase.

The analysis conducted at the bottom of sample 11 is presented in Figure 4.18.

Figure 4.18: X-ray analysis conducted at the bottom of sample 11.

As for the centre, there is one area close to the bottom in which only iron is detected, while FeB was detected in the point analysis. There is a stronger signal for silicon in some phases at the bottom, which was found to be SiC in the point analysis. However, as previously pointed out, no carbon was detected in these areas. Aluminium was once again found to be evenly distributed in the sample, but with slightly higher concentrations in the SiB₆ phase.

4.3 SEM analysis

All samples were analysed in SEM to investigate the formation of the different phases. The samples appeared to be very similar, hence only images from samples that are representative for the three different types of experiments are included below.

Images obtained from sample 10 is presented in Figure 4.19. This sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure 4.19: The figure shows images obtained from sample 10 at different magnifications in SEM. The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

In these images, the same phases as detected in EPMA can be observed. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage.

Images obtained from sample 13 is presented in Figure 4.20. This sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 13 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 13 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 13 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 13 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure 4.20: The figure shows images obtained from sample 13 at different magnifications in SEM. The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to two cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

The images from samples subjected to one and two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C appear very similar. Once again, it appears like SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage.

Images obtained from sample 18 is presented in Figure 4.21. This sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100$ °C.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 200x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 250x magnification in SEM.

Figure 4.21: The figure shows images obtained from sample 18 at different magnifications in SEM. The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 100$ °C.

The images obtained from samples subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100$ °C appear to be slightly different from the samples subjected to $T_m \pm 20$ °C. Less SiB_6 can be observed, while more Si_4BFe_4 seems to have formed. These samples also appear to be more eutectic. Some B_4C can also be observed in these samples, which may indicate that more carbon has dissolved in the alloy in these samples.

4.4 LOM analysis

In the experiments previously performed by the author (2017)^{[28][29]}, silicon had penetrated into the crucible and formed SiC in all samples, and the penetration depth could be seen with the naked eye after polishing. The penetration of silicon in the crucible could also be seen with the naked eye in the Si-B reference sample, as seen in Figure 4.22a. However, no penetration depth could be seen with the naked eye in any of the samples containing Fe-Si-B alloy, as seen in Figure 4.22b and Figure 4.22c.

(a) The figure shows the Si-B reference sample after mounting, grinding, and polishing. After polishing, the penetration depth of silicon into the graphite crucible could be seen with the naked eye, as indicated by the red marker. (b) Sample 12 after mounting, grinding, and polishing. This sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C. (c) Sample 15 after mounting, grinding, and polishing. This sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 100$ °C.

Figure 4.22: Images show three crucibles after mounting, grinding, and polishing. Unlike the Si-B reference sample, no penetration of silicon into the graphite crucible could be observed with the naked eye in any of the samples containing Fe-Si-B alloy.

The crucibles from all successful experiments were investigated in LOM to determine the degree of silicon penetration, and the dark areas close to the crucible surface was assumed to be SiC. The samples containing Fe-Si-B alloy appeared to be very similar, hence only images obtained from samples representative for the three different types of experiments are included.

Images obtained at 2.5x magnification from the Si-B reference sample are presented in Figure 4.23.

(a) The image is obtained from the bottom of the crucible in the Si-B reference sample. Large amounts of SiC can be observed as dark areas in the crucible.

(b) The image is obtained from the left corner of the crucible in the Si-B reference sample. A pore had formed in the corner of the sample, but some SiC can still be observed as dark areas around the corner.

(c) The image is obtained from the left wall of the crucible the Si-B reference sample. Large amounts of SiC can be observed as dark areas in the crucible.

(d) The image is obtained from the left wall of the crucible the Si-B reference sample. Large amounts of SiC can be observed as dark areas in the crucible.

Figure 4.23: The figure shows images obtained from the Si-B reference sample at 2.5x magnification in LOM. The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

Large amounts of SiC could be observed in the crucible of the Si-B reference sample at both 2.5x and 10x magnification. This was expected due to the high silicon content and good wetting properties of silicon on graphite. The same behaviour was observed in the experiments previously conducted by the author (2017)^[28]^[29].

Images obtained at 2.5x magnification from sample 12 are presented in Figure 4.24.

(a) The image is obtained from the bottom of the crucible in sample 12. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(b) The image is obtained from the left corner of the crucible in sample 12. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(c) The image is obtained from the left wall of the crucible in sample 12. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(d) The image is obtained from the left wall towards the top of the crucible of sample 12. No penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

Figure 4.24: The figure shows images obtained from sample 12 at 2.5x magnification in LOM. The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

Very little SiC could be observed in the crucible of the Fe-Si-B samples subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

Images obtained at 2.5x magnification from sample 13 are presented in Figure 4.25.

(a) The image is obtained from the bottom of the crucible in sample 13. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(b) The image is obtained from the left corner of the crucible in sample 13. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(c) The image is obtained from the left wall of the crucible in sample 13. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(d) The image is obtained from the left wall towards the top of the crucible of sample 13. No penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

Figure 4.25: The figure shows images obtained from sample 13 at 2.5x magnification in LOM. The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to two cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

Very little SiC could be observed in the crucible of the Fe-Si-B samples subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to two cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C.

Images obtained at 2.5x magnification from sample 15 are presented in Figure 4.26.

(a) The image is obtained from the bottom of the crucible in sample 15. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(b) The image is obtained from the left corner of the crucible in sample 15. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

(c) The image is obtained from the left wall of the crucible in sample 15. Very little penetration of silicon in the crucible could be observed in this area.

Figure 4.26: The figure shows images obtained from sample 15 at 2.5x magnification in LOM. The sample was subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to two cycles between $T_m \pm 100$ °C.

Very little SiC could be observed in the crucible of the Fe-Si-B samples subjected to 1550 °C for 1h before being exposed to one cycle between $T_m \pm 100$ °C.

The penetration depth of silicon into the graphite crucible was analysed in iSolution. The measurements were performed on the Si-B reference sample, and one sample representable for the crucibles containing Fe-Si-B alloy. The penetration depth was measured at 20 positions in the bottom, left corner, and left wall of the crucibles, as seen in Figure 4.27 and Figure 4.28.

(a) 20 measurements of the penetration depth were obtained at the bottom of the crucible in the Si-B reference sample.

(b) 20 measurements of the penetration depth were obtained at the corner of the crucible in the Si-B reference sample.

(c) 20 measurements of the penetration depth were obtained at the wall of the crucible in the Si-B reference sample.

Figure 4.27: The figure presents how the penetration depth at the bottom, corner, and wall of the crucible in the Si-B reference sample was measured in iSolution.

(a) 20 measurements of the penetration depth were obtained at the bottom of the crucible in sample 10.

(b) 20 measurements of the penetration depth were obtained at the corner of the crucible in sample 10.

(c) 20 measurements of the penetration depth were obtained at the wall of the crucible in sample 10.

Figure 4.28: The figure presents how the penetration depth at the bottom, corner, and wall of the crucible in sample 10 was measured in iSolution.

The mean values of the measurements obtained from the two samples are presented in Table 4.15.

Table 4.15: The table contains mean values with standard deviations of the measured penetration depth of silicon into the bottom, left corner, and left wall of the crucible. The measurements are obtained from the reference sample (Si-B alloy) and sample 10 (Fe-Si-B alloy).

Alloy	Bottom	Std. Dev.	Corner	Std. Dev.	Wall	Std. Dev.
	[μm]					
Si-B	2430	160	880	270	1410	300
Fe-Si-B	120	60	80	40	70	30

As seen from both images obtained in LOM at 2.5x magnification and the measurements conducted in iSolution, the crucibles containing Fe-Si-B alloy experienced significantly less penetration of silicon into the crucible compared to the Si-B reference sample. The author conducted similar measurements from ten samples in previous work^[28]. The median penetration depth in these samples were found to be 1150 μm at the bottom, 1150 μm at the corner, and 830 μm at the wall of the crucible, which is comparable to the results obtained from the Si-B reference sample.

4.4.1 The effect of volume expansion on the crucible

A possible complication in the experiments conducted around the eutectic temperature is crack formation in the crucible during solidification due to the volume expansion. A crack was observed in the crucible of sample 17, as seen in Figure 4.29. However, it was located at the outer part of the crucible and had propagated inwards, which indicates that the crack most likely occurred during cutting of the sample.

Figure 4.29: The image is obtained from the corner of the crucible in sample 17, at 2.5x magnification in LOM. A crack was observed in the upper part of the image. The scratch that can be observed in the bottom occurred during polishing.

No cracks could be observed in any of the other crucibles. However, the volume of the samples in the experiments were the about 1/3 the size of the crucibles, and a larger sample volume will result in larger tension on the crucible. To investigate the effect of volume expansion on the crucible, an experiment was thus conducted with 12 g of alloy instead of 6 g. As seen in sample 17, crack formation might occur in the crucible during cutting, hence the sample was mounted without cutting. The crucible was grinded down until the alloy was visible, and then polished. The crucible was investigated in LOM, and as seen in Figure 4.30, no cracks could be observed in the crucible.

(a) The image is obtained at the bottom of sample 19. (b) The image is obtained at the corner of sample 19.

(c) The image is obtained at the lower left wall of sample 19. (d) The image is obtained at the upper left wall of sample 19.

Figure 4.30: The figure presents images obtained from the crucible in sample 19 at 2.5x magnification. No cracks could be observed in any parts of the crucible.

4.5 Wetting tests

Unlike the Si-B alloys, most of the Fe-Si-B alloys could easily be removed from the crucibles after cutting. This may indicate that Fe-Si-B has less wetting abilities on graphite compared to the Si-B alloys. To further investigate the wetting properties of the Fe-Si-B alloy, samples from the master alloy was given to Research Scientist Sarina Bao, SINTEF Industry, for testing. Several wetting tests were performed with different conditions, as seen in Table 4.16.

Table 4.16: The table presents the conditions and results from the wetting tests performed by Reaserch Scientist Sarina Bao, SINTEF Indistry. All samples were initially heated with a rate of 4 °C/min up to 1150 °C, and the heating rate was varied from this point.

Test	Substrate	Atm	Pre-treatment	Heating rate	T _m
1	Graphite	Ar	None	5 °C/min up to 1550 °C	1200 °C
2	Graphite	Vacuum	None	5 °C/min up to 1550 °C	1226 °C
3	Graphite	Vacuum	None	2 °C/min up to 1250 °C	Not melted
4	Graphite	Vacuum	None	2 °C/min up to 1250 °C	Not melted
5	Graphite	Vacuum	Acid bath	5 °C/min up to 1550 °C	1217 °C
6	Alumina	Vacuum	Acid bath	10 °C/min up to 1550 °C	1251 °C
7	Graphite	Vacuum	Acid bath	10 °C/min up to 1550 °C	1225 °C
8	Alumina	Vacuum	Acid bath	10 °C/min up to 1550 °C	1228 °C

Images obtained at different temperatures during the wetting tests are presented in the next pages.

Figure 4.31 presents the images obtained during wetting test 1.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 1 at 1198 °C.

(b) The figure shows the sample in test 1 at 1199 °C.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 1 at 1200 °C. A bubble of erupted liquid could be observed at this temperature.

(d) The figure shows the sample in test 1 at 1399 °C. The sample did not completely melt during this test.

Figure 4.31: The figure presents the sample in test 1 at different temperatures. A bubble of liquid erupted at 1200 °C, which indicates that the alloy started to melt at this temperature. The sample did not reach complete melting, and the most probable cause of the uneven melting is an oxide layer present on the sample surface.

A bubble of liquid erupted at the top of the sample at 1200 °C in test 1, as seen in Figure 4.31c, and the sample did not reach complete melting. This may indicate that there was an oxide layer on the surface of the sample, which altered the melting temperature.

Figure 4.32 presents the images obtained during wetting test 2.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 2 at 1198 °C.

(b) The figure shows the sample in test 2 at 1226 °C. Signs of melting occurred at the bottom of the sample at this temperature.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 2 at 1228 °C.

(d) The figure shows the sample in test 2 at 1234 °C. Complete melting was obtained at this temperature.

Figure 4.32: The figure presents the sample in test 2 at different temperatures. The sample started to melt from the bottom at approx. 1226 °C, and complete melting was obtained at 1234 °C. The contact angle was measured to be 109°, which indicates low wettability.

The second test was performed in vacuum instead of in argon atmosphere to see if the problem with uneven melting could be avoided. This sample started to melt at the bottom at approx. 1226 °C as seen in Figure 4.32b. Complete melting was achieved at 1234 °C and the contact angle was measured to be 109°, which indicates low wettability. Since this test showed more even melting, the further tests were also performed in vacuum.

Figure 4.33 presents the images obtained during wetting test 3.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 3 at 1198 °C.

(b) The figure shows the sample in test 3 at 1226 °C.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 3 at 1228 °C.

Figure 4.33: The figure presents the sample in test 3 at different temperatures. The sample did not melt, even after being held at 1250 °C for 1h and 30min. The reason behind this behaviour is unclear.

The sample was heated to 1250 °C and held at this temperature for 1h and 30min in the third test, but the sample did not melt as seen in Figure 4.33. It is unclear why this happened, but it could possibly be caused by heterogeneous composition of the master alloy.

Figure 4.34 presents the images obtained during wetting test 4.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 4 at 1198 °C. (b) The figure shows the sample in test 4 at 1226 °C.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 4 at 1228 °C.

Figure 4.34: The figure presents the sample in test 4 at different temperatures. The sample did not melt, even after being held at 1300 °C for 20min. The reason is considered to be due to an oxide layer on the surface of the sample.

In test 4, the sample was heated to 1300 °C and held at this temperature for 20min, but it did not melt as seen in Figure 4.34. During the holding time the pressure increased from 0.1 mbar up to 0.33 mbar before it decreased again, which might indicate the presence of an oxide layer. It was thus decided to submerge the samples in acid prior to conducting any further tests, to remove any possible oxide layer present on the sample surfaces.

Figure 4.35 presents the images obtained during wetting test 5.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 5 at 1214 °C.

(b) The figure shows the sample in test 5 at 1217 °C. Signs of melting occurred at the bottom of the sample at this temperature.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 5 at 1219 °C.

(d) The figure shows the sample in test 5 at 1253 °C. The window towards the camera blacked out at this temperature, as seen in the figure.

Figure 4.35: The figure presents the sample in test 5 at different temperatures. The sample showed signs of melting at the bottom at 1217 °C, but the window towards the camera blacked out at approx. 1253 °C.

In test 5, the sample was submerged in an acid bath prior to the test to remove any possible oxide layer present on the surface. Signs of melting at the bottom of the sample occurred at 1217 °C as seen in Figure 4.35c. However, the window towards the camera blacked out during the test at approx. 1253 °C as seen in Figure 4.35d, and the test had to be terminated.

Figure 4.36 presents the images obtained during wetting test 6.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 6 at 1224 °C.

(b) The figure shows the sample in test 6 at 1251 °C. Signs of melting occurred at the bottom of the sample at this temperature.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 6 at 1354 °C. The sample had obtained complete melting at this temperature.

(d) The figure shows the sample in test 6 at 1536 °C. The sample showed low wettability at this temperature.

Figure 4.36: The figure presents the sample in test 6 at different temperatures. The test was performed on alumina substrate. The sample showed signs of melting at the bottom at 1251 °C and complete melting was observed at 1536 °C. The contact angle was measured to be 124°, which indicates low wettability.

In test 6, the substrate was changed from graphite to alumina to compare the wetting properties of the alloy on these two materials. The sample started to melt at 1250 °C, and complete melting was obtained at 1353 °C. The contact angle between the substrate and the alloy was measured to be 124°, which indicates low wettability.

Figure 4.37 presents the images obtained during wetting test 7.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 7 at 1211 °C.

(b) The figure shows the sample in test 7 at 1225 °C. Signs of melting occurred at the bottom of the sample at this temperature.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 7 at 1380 °C. The sample had obtained complete melting at this temperature.

(d) The figure shows the sample in test 7 at 1428 °C. The sample showed high wettability at this temperature.

Figure 4.37: The figure presents the sample in test 7 at different temperatures. The sample showed signs of melting at the bottom at 1225 °C. The contact angle was measured to be 31° at 1428 °C, which indicates high wettability.

Test 7 was performed on graphite. The sample showed signs of melting at the bottom at 1225 °C, as seen in Figure 4.37b. Complete melting was observed at approx. 1380 °C, as seen in Figure 4.37c. The contact angle between the substrate and the alloy was measured to be 31° at 1428 °C, which indicates high wettability.

Figure 4.38 presents the images obtained during wetting test 8.

(a) The figure shows the sample in test 8 at 1212 °C.

(b) The figure shows the sample in test 8 at 1228 °C. Signs of melting appeared at the bottom of the sample at this temperature.

(c) The figure shows the sample in test 8 at 1234 °C.

(d) The figure shows the sample in test 8 at 1257 °C. Complete melting could be observed at this temperature, and the sample showed low wettability.

Figure 4.38: The figure presents the sample in test 8 at different temperatures. The sample showed signs of melting at the bottom at 1228 °C. Complete melting was observed at 1257 °C. The contact angle was measured to be 120°, which indicates low wettability.

Test 8 was performed on alumina. The sample showed signs of melting at the bottom at 1228 °C, as seen in Figure 4.38b. Complete melting was observed at approx. 1257 °C, as seen in Figure 4.38d. The contact angle between the substrate and the alloy was measured to be 120°, which indicates low wettability.

After the first three tests were performed, it was decided to analyse the phase composition of these samples in SEM. This was done to investigate if heterogeneity of the master alloy was the reason behind the deviating results obtained in the tests. The images obtained from the wetting samples were compared to those obtained from the samples from the main experiments presented in Section 4.3.

The images obtained from the sample in test 1 is presented in Figure 4.39. As seen from the figure, only two phases could be detected in this sample. It appears like the lighter grey phase was precipitated at a higher temperature. The darker grey phase was most likely precipitated at a lower temperature, and the distribution of this phase appears to be eutectic. This sample clearly deviates in phase composition compared to the samples investigated in Section 4.3.

(a) The image is obtained from the sample in test 1 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from the sample in test 1 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from the sample in test 1 at 200x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from the sample in test 1 at 400x magnification in SEM.

Figure 4.39: The figure shows images obtained from the sample in test 1 at different magnifications in SEM. Only two phases can be observed in this sample, but the composition appears to be eutectic.

The images obtained from the sample in test 2 is presented in Figure 4.40. As seen from the figure, only two phases could be detected in this sample as well. Once again, it appears like the lighter grey phase was precipitated at a higher temperature, while the darker grey phase was most likely precipitated at a lower temperature. The distribution of the darker phase appears to be eutectic in this sample as well.

(a) The image is obtained from the sample in test 2 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from the sample in test 2 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from the sample in test 2 at 200x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from the sample in test 2 at 400x magnification in SEM.

Figure 4.40: The figure shows images obtained from the sample in test 2 at different magnifications in SEM.

The images obtained from the sample in test 3 is presented in Figure 4.41. Three different phases could be observed in this sample, and the composition appears similar to the composition found in the main samples presented in Section 4.3.

(a) The image is obtained from the sample in test 3, at 100x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from the sample in test 3, at 150x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from the sample in test 3, at 200x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from the sample in test 3, at 400x magnification in SEM.

Figure 4.41: The figure shows images obtained from the sample in test 3 at different magnifications in SEM.

No direct correlation between the phase distribution of the samples and the result from the wetting tests could be found. The most reasonable cause behind the deviations is thus considered to be oxide layers present on the sample surfaces, as previously suspected.

4.6 Mass loss

The amount (%) of mass lost during the experiments is listed in Table 4.17, and plotted against temperature in Figure 4.42 and time in Figure 4.43.

Table 4.17: Log of performed experiments, where m_1 is the weight of crucible prior to experiment, m_2 is the weight of crucible and weighed out powder prior to experiment, and m_3 is the weight of the sample after the experiment.

Sample	m_1 [g]	m_2 [g]	m_3 [g]	Percent loss [%]
M.A.	186.91	286.91	285.76	1.15
9	13.54	19.42	19.41	0.23
10	13.56	19.50	19.48	0.29
11	13.42	19.40	19.39	0.20
12	13.44	19.32	19.30	0.23
13	13.57	19.48	19.46	0.30
14	13.42	19.26	19.24	0.21
15	13.59	19.55	19.54	0.24
16	13.55	19.52	19.50	0.21
17	13.57	19.53	19.51	0.34
18	12.59	19.52	19.50	0.26
19	13.46	25.75	25.73	0.12

It can be observed in Figure 4.42 that the master alloy, which was subjected to 1750°C, experienced a considerate mass loss compared to the other samples. However, the composition of the master alloy was confirmed to be close to the intended composition by ICP-MS analysis, as described in Section 4.1. This indicates that this mass loss did not have a considerable effect on the composition of the alloy.

Figure 4.42: The graph expresses the percent of mass lost during the experiments as a function of temperature.

As seen in Figure 4.43 and Table 4.17, all other samples had a loss of 0.12-0.34 %, hence it is safe to assume that the alloys maintained the desired composition throughout the experiments.

Figure 4.43: The graph expresses the percent of mass lost during the experiments as a function of time.

4.7 Experimental challenges

For the initial experiments, approx. 5 g of the raw materials were thoroughly mixed together and added to the crucible. Three experiments were conducted with a temperature interval between $T_m \pm 20$ °C. After cutting, it was observed that the raw materials had not fully melted to form an alloy, as seen in Figure 4.44a. A new experiment was conducted in which the temperature interval was increased to $T_m \pm 30$ °C. The raw materials did still not melt properly as seen in Figure 4.44b, and the experiment was once again considered unsuccessful.

(a) The figure shows a cross section of sample 3. The sample was heated to 1177 °C and kept for 1 h before cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C were initiated. The raw materials did not melt down properly.

(b) The figure shows a cross section of sample 6. The temperature interval was increased to $T_m \pm 30$ °C, but the raw materials did still not melt down properly.

Figure 4.44: Images shows cross sections of sample 3 and sample 6 which were considered unsuccessful.

To investigate if the unsuccessful experiments were caused by malfunctioning thermocouples, a calibration was performed. This was done by conducting an experiment on a sample of pure copper, which has a melting temperature of 1085 °C. The copper sample was exposed to 1115 °C for 10 minutes, and the sample had melted completely as seen in Figure 4.45. This indicates that the thermocouples were well functioning and another approach for the experiments had to be chosen.

Figure 4.45: The figure shows the melted copper sample in the graphite crucible. This confirmed that the thermocouples were well functioning.

In the experiments conducted by the author during the autumn of 2017^[28], the samples containing silicon and boron powder were heated to 1550 °C and kept at this temperature for 1 h before cycles were initiated in the liquidus state. There were no trouble with melting of the alloys during these experiments, and a similar approach was applied for the next experiment. The powders were layered in the crucible, in which iron was located at the bottom, and silicon and boron was thoroughly mixed and added on top. The sample was heated to 1550 °C and kept for 1 h, before one cycle between $T_m \pm 20$ °C was initiated. The sample was melted down, but it appeared like the raw materials had not mixed well during melting, as seen in Figure 4.46. It appeared like silicon and boron had reacted with the crucible and formed carbides in the upper part of the sample, while iron had melted towards the bottom.

Figure 4.46: The figure shows a cross section of sample 7, which was heated to 1550 °C and kept for 1 h before cycles were initiated.

The sample was mounted, grinded, and polished before being investigated in LOM. As seen in Figure 4.47, substantial amounts of carbides were observed in the upper parts of the sample as suspected.

(a) The wall of sample 7, investigated in LOM at 5x magnification. SiC can be observed as the grey phase in the sample. It can also be observed that silicon has penetrated into the graphite to form SiC by the dark grey areas of the walls.

(b) The top of sample 7, investigated in LOM at 5x magnification. Large amounts of SiC can be observed at the top area of the sample.

(c) The middle of sample 7, investigated in LOM at 5x magnification. In this image it can clearly be observed that SiC had formed in the upper part of the sample, while iron had melted at the bottom.

Figure 4.47: Images are obtained from sample 7 by light optical microscope at 5x magnification. Significant amounts of SiC was observed in the top parts of the sample.

It was suspected that lack of sufficient contact between the three components were the reason behind the unmelted samples, and that the formation of carbides in the top of sample 7 was caused by lack of mixing during melting. Hence, it was decided to make a pre-melted master alloy.

Since Fe-Si-B reacts with graphite at high temperatures, an alternative crucible material during preparation of the master alloy was considered. A small scale experiment was performed on eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy in an alumina crucible, to investigate the interaction at high temperatures. Figure 4.48 presents the crucible with alloy after the experiment. The sample had melted, but could still easily be removed from the crucible. It was thus decided to prepare the master alloy in an alumina crucible.

Figure 4.48: The figure presents the alumina crucible with the melted alloy after the small scale experiment. The alloy could easily be removed from the crucible, which indicates that very little interactions occurred between the alloy and the crucible during operation.

5 Discussion

The following section will provide a discussion of the obtained results, which will be compared to previous work on eutectic Si-B alloy performed by the author (2017)^[28]^[29].

The penetration depth of silicon into the graphite crucible could be observed with the naked eye in the eutectic Si-B reference sample. This could also be observed for all the samples in the previous work performed by the author on eutectic Si-B alloy. However, no such penetration could be observed with the naked eye in any of the samples containing Fe-Si-B alloy. During investigation of the samples containing Fe-Si-B alloy in LOM at 2.5x and 10x magnification, very little penetration of silicon into the graphite crucibles could be observed. The penetration depth in the Si-B reference sample, however, was found to be severe. The images obtained in LOM were analysed in iSolution, and the penetration depth was measured to be approx. 20x deeper into the crucible in the sample containing eutectic Si-B, compared to eutectic Fe-Si-B. The measured penetration depth in the Si-B reference sample were comparable to those previously conducted by the author on eutectic Si-B alloy. This result indicates that the eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy has a less degrading effect on carbon crucibles compared to eutectic Si-B alloy, which is promising for the intended application.

As previously mentioned, all samples except one could easily be removed from the crucible after cutting. Due to this, in addition to the low amount of silicon penetration in the crucible, it was assumed that the alloy had low wetting abilities on graphite. However, according to theory presented in Section 2.4.5.1, studies show that both pure iron and ferrosilicon alloys exhibit good wetting properties on graphite at temperatures in the range of 1300-1500 °C. Wetting tests were therefore performed to further investigate the wetting behaviour of Fe-Si-B on graphite and alumina. A summary of the measured contact angles and wetting behaviour of eutectic Fe-Si-B are included in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: The table presents the contact angles measured from the samples that melted down completely in the wetting tests performed on eutectic Fe-Si-B.

Test	Substrate	θ_{con} [°]	Wetting behaviour
2	Graphite	109	Low wettability
6	Alumina	124	Low wettability
7	Graphite	31	High wettability
8	Alumina	120	Low wettability

Only two of the wetting tests performed on graphite reached complete melting, in which the alloy in test 2 showed low wettability, while the alloy in test 7 showed high wettability. The sample in test 2 had no pre-treatment, while the sample in test 7 was submerged in acid prior to the test. Three of the four tests performed without pre-treatment were considered unsuccessful, and it was therefore assumed that an oxide layer was present on the surface of the samples. This was also supported by the increase of pressure observed during test 3, which was likely caused by the reaction:

The SEM analysis of the alloy in test 1, test 2, and test 3 did not present any possible reason for the difference in melting. Consequently, the alloy in test 2 most likely showed low wettability due to an oxide layer present on the surface as first assumed, and the result from test 7 is therefore emphasised.

High wettability might increase the penetration depth of silicon, and thus the degradation of the crucible. Pure silicon has been reported with contact angles of $< 30^\circ$, which is comparable to the contact angle between Fe-Si-B and graphite obtained in test 7. It can thus be assumed that eutectic Fe-Si-B has similar wettability to eutectic Si-B on graphite. Even though the Fe-Si-B alloy was found to have high wettability on graphite, very little penetration of silicon was observed in the crucible as previously mentioned. Hence, it is assumed that the high wettability will not be a challenge in the intended application.

The formation of SiC is controlled by the activity of silicon in the alloy. If the activity of silicon in the alloy is greater than the activity of pure Si (l) at a certain temperature, the formation of SiC will occur. The activity of liquid silicon, silicon in the alloy at 1157 °C, and silicon in the alloy at 1550 °C in equilibrium with carbon and SiC is presented as a function of temperature in Figure 5.1. It can be observed that the activity of silicon in the alloy is greater than the activity in liquid silicon at both temperatures, which indicates that the formation of SiC is possible.

Figure 5.1: The figure presents the activity of liquid silicon, silicon in the alloy at 1157 °C, and silicon in the alloy at 1550 °C in equilibrium with carbon and SiC as a function of temperature. The activities were calculated in FactSage by Jian Meng Jiao using the FT Lite database. The activity of silicon in the alloy is greater than the activity of pure liquid silicon at both temperatures.

In the previous experiments on Si-B alloy performed by the author, a barrier layer of SiC could be observed along the entire interface between the alloy and the crucible. This could also be observed along the bottom and wall of the reference sample. No contentious barrier layer could be observed in any of the Fe-Si-B alloys, however, some single SiC particles were observed towards the edge of the samples in EPMA. Silicon is generally a very reactive material, and the saturation of SiC in the alloy over time is

highly unwanted in the intended application. In addition, the presence of oxygen in the system may lead to slag formation and degassing according to the reactions presented below:

A low activity of silicon in the alloy is therefore desired. In Figure 2.28 in Section 2.4.5.3, the activity of silicon is found to decrease with increasing amount of iron in the FeSi system. In addition, the activity of silicon in the Fe-Si-B alloy was found to be 0.14 at 1157 °C and 0.21 at 1550 °C in Figure 5.1, while the activity of silicon in eutectic Si-B alloy is significantly higher at approx. 0.92. This indicates that silicon is less reactive in the Fe-Si-B alloy, and less SiC will thus be formed during operation compared to eutectic Si-B alloy. This is in accordance with the obtained results in this thesis. It also indicates that the alloy will experience less degassing and slag formation if oxygen accesses the system, compared to eutectic Si-B alloy.

As earlier presented in Section 2.4.5.2, the carbon dissolution is reported to decrease with increasing iron content for alloys with silicon content of <20 wt.% Si according to Chipman *et al.* (1951)^[10], while the dissolution is increasing with increasing iron content for alloys with >50 wt.% Si according to Ottem (1993)^[56]. The Fe-Si-B alloy investigated in this thesis has a silicon content of 26 wt.% Si, which is in a transition area according to this theory. When work previously done by the author on eutectic Si-B alloy is compared to the current work, it is clear that less SiC has formed in the Fe-Si-B alloy. No B₄C was found in the previous work, however, this was most likely due to the low boron content of the alloy. Some B₄C was found in the current work, but the total amount of carbon present in the Fe-Si-B alloy still appears to be lower than in the eutectic Si-B alloy previously investigated by the author. This indicates that less carbon dissolves in the Fe-Si-B alloy compared to the Si-B alloy.

No cracks caused by volume expansion could be observed in any of the crucibles. The volume expansion of Fe-Si-B was calculated to be $dV = -0.01 \text{ [cm}^3/\text{cm}^3]$ with the assumption of ideal mixing, which indicates that the alloy shrinks during solidification. The area of a cross section of the sample in test 8 was measured at different temperatures, as presented

in in Figure 5.2. The measurements are presented graphically graphically in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.2: The figure presents how the area of the sample in wetting test 8 was measured in iSolution.

Figure 5.3: The graph expresses the change in volume of the sample in wetting test 8 during solidification. The volume was found to be shrinking during solidification.

The theoretical melting temperature of 1157 °C is marked in Figure 5.3. Some outliers can be observed in the graph at 1300 °C and 1120 °C, which may be caused by the presence of oxygen in pores in the sample, and it appears like the sample experienced undercooling. This makes it difficult to investigate exactly what happens during solidification. An approximate melting pattern can be observed as marked in the figure, in which it appears like very little volume change takes place until the theoretical melting temperature of 1157 °C is reached. After this point, the volume appears to be shrinking. The shrinkage in volume is the most reasonable cause behind the reduced contact surface between the alloy and the crucible, and not low wettability as first assumed. Damage to the crucibles due to volume expansion during solidification has previously been considered a technical challenge for the intended application. The shrinkage in volume of the Fe-Si-B alloy is therefore considered a desirable material property.

It was important to investigate the phase composition of the alloy to determine if a

eutectic composition was reached, and to gain general knowledge about the system. Five different phases were identified by EPMA analysis. This includes FeB and Si_4BFe_4 as matrices, SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$ spread across the entire samples, and SiC particles located at the edge of the samples. Two modifications of boron carbide were found, namely B_4C and $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$. B_4C was formed as particles in the same areas as SiC, while $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ appeared to have formed in small amounts in the entire sample. The $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ was found to contain more boron compared to B_4C , in addition to slightly more aluminium.

Since FeB and Si_4BFe_4 were detected as matrices, these phases were most likely precipitated in the liquidus state. SiC and B_4C were observed as particles, which also indicates that these phases precipitated at temperatures above the eutectic point. Figure 5.4 presents an alloy with eutectic composition. When the images obtained in SEM presented in Section 4.3 and Appendix C are compared to these images, it appears like SiB_6 , $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$, and $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ are eutectic phases.

(a) The alloy consists of 30% Pb and 70% Sn. (b) The alloy consists of 37% Pb and 63% Sn. (c) The alloy consists of 50% Pb and 50% Sn.

Figure 5.4: The figure presents typical eutectic solidification structure of an alloy. The alloy is Pb-Sn of different compositions. The images are taken from Metallografisk Atlas (1987)^[31].

The phase distribution of the alloys subjected to $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$, presented in Figure 4.21 in Section 4.3, appears to be more eutectic compared to the other samples. The phase distribution of the samples subjected to one and two samples appeared to be fairly similar, which indicates that the phase composition is more dependent on temperature than on the number of cycles.

The eutectic temperature of the alloy is 1157 °C. However, it must be pointed out that this temperature is for a Fe-Si-B system that is not carbon saturated. The samples in the wetting tests showed signs of melting in the range between 1200-1250 °C, and the higher melting temperatures are most likely due to carbon saturation.

As stated in Section 3.1, the alloy should consist of approx. 68 % FeSi, 24 % FeB, and 8 % SiB₆. However, FeSi was not detected in the EPMA analysis, while two three-phase compounds were identified. The quaternary phase diagram of the Fe-Si-B-C system, in which three-phase compounds are included, was not investigated. It is thus uncertain if these phases are metastable, or if they are stable due to carbon saturation in the alloy. It is also possible that the detected composition of the boron containing compounds are incorrect due to the low atomic number of boron.

An image of sample 10 obtained at 60x magnification in SEM was analysed in iSolution to investigate the area% of the different phases present in the alloy. Figure 5.5 presents how the area% of the matrix was measured. The sample was found to consist of approx. 70 % matrix, 9 % dark phase and 21 % light phase.

Figure 5.5: The figure presents how the area% of the matrix was measured in iSolution. The area% of the matrix was found to be approx. 70 %.

Since no FeSi was detected in the alloy, while approx. 70 % of Si₄BFe₄ was found in the

matrix, FeSi might have been falsely detected as this phase due to inaccurate identification of boron in EPMA. The light phase was identified as $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$ in EPMA, which does not correspond to the theoretical phase composition of the alloy. Small amounts of FeB was detected as matrix in the EPMA analysis, while 24 % FeB should be present in the alloy. The dark phase was identified as SiB_6 in EPMA, which corresponds well to the theoretical amount of SiB_6 that should be present in the alloy.

The composition of the phases detected in EPMA is presented in the ternary phase diagram of Fe-Si-B in Figure 5.6. As seen in this figure, Si_4BFe_4 is located in the FeSi region, which might support the suspicion that Si_4BFe_4 was misinterpreted as FeSi in the EPMA analysis.

Figure 5.6: The figure presents the composition of the phases identified in the EPMA analysis in the Fe-Si-B ternary diagram.

The exact composition of the master alloy was important to determine to ensure that the obtained results are representative for the alloy in consideration. It was also important to determine the impurities present in the alloy, since this might affect the material properties. The results from the ICP-MS analysis are presented in the ternary phase diagram in Figure 5.7, in which it can be observed that the obtained composition was very close to the ideal composition of the alloy. Other than the alloying elements, only very small concentrations of Al and Mn were detected. Aluminium was found to be evenly distributed in the samples by X-ray analysis in EPMA, but with slightly higher concentrations in SiB_6 and $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$.

Figure 5.7: The figure presents the composition determined by ICP-MS in the ternary phase diagram. It can be observed that the master alloy was very close to the ideal composition.

Only 0.12-0.34 % mass was lost during the experiments, hence it can be assumed that the composition of the alloys were close to ideal for all samples.

The small scale experiment performed on the alloy in alumina crucible indicated that the Fe-Si-B alloy has low reactivity with alumina, which is also supported by the low concentration of aluminium detected in the master alloy by ICP-MS. Two wetting tests were performed on alumina, in which Fe-Si-B showed low wettability. These results indicate that alumina might be a possible alternative crucible material for eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy in LHTES systems.

As previously mentioned in Section 3.7, it was difficult to obtain sufficient contact between the three components to form an alloy. The iron and boron powder had a very fine particle size, while silicon granules were used. The total surface area is greater for smaller particles, which also leads to a larger amount of oxides present. Hence, using larger particles might increase the possibility for an alloy to form. Another possible solution might be to layer the raw materials by descending melting temperature, as illustrated in Figure 5.8. Silicon has the lowest melting temperature, and should thus be placed on top. Silicon will then melt and run towards the bottom of the crucible while it mixes with the other two components. A possible challenge with this approach is the formation of silicon carbide prior to melting of iron and boron, as seen in sample 7 in which a similar approach was applied.

Figure 5.8: The figure illustrates a crucible layered with powder by melting temperature.

Comparison of Fe-Si-B and Si-B

The advantages and disadvantages of both eutectic Fe-Si-B and eutectic Si-B are summarised in Table 5.2, in which eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy appears to be highly suitable for the intended application.

Table 5.2: The table presents the advantages and disadvantages of eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy and eutectic Si-B alloy.

	Pros	Cons
Fe-Si-B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High fusion enthalpy (3.67 kJ/cm³) ● Low volume change during solidification ● Slow degradation of the crucible ● Low wettability on Al₂O₃ (120°) ● Low reactivity on Al₂O₃ ● Cheaper? ● Low T_m (1157°C) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High wettability on graphite (30°)
Si-B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High fusion enthalpy (4.42 kJ/cm³) ● Crucible transforms into more dense SiC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High wettability on graphite (<30°) ● High reactivity with graphite ● Faster degradation of the crucible ● High volume expansion during solidification ● More expensive? ● Higher T_m (1385°C)

6 Conclusion

This thesis was devoted to investigate possible alloys for the application in latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) units. The alloy must be a phase change material, in which a large amount of energy is released during solidification, have a low volume expansion during operation, and low reactivity with the crucible material. The eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy with 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si and 9 wt.% B proved to be the perfect candidate for the intended application. To investigate the interaction between eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy and graphite crucibles, experiments were conducted in a resistance heated furnace in 5N Ar (g) atmosphere, in which the samples were subjected to one or two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20$ °C and $T_m \pm 100$ °C. The samples were investigated in EPMA, SEM, and LOM, and wetting tests on graphite and alumina were performed. Previous work has been performed by the author on eutectic Si-B alloy during the summer and autumn of 2017^[28]^[29], which will be compared to the results obtained in this thesis.

According to the investigations in LOM, very little silicon had penetrated into the crucible to form SiC. Previous work performed by the author showed that eutectic Si-B alloy will penetrate the crucible significantly, in which it is assumed that the crucible will be completely transformed into SiC over time. It can thus be concluded that eutectic Fe-Si-B has a lower degrading effect on the crucible compared to eutectic Si-B, which is desirable for the intended application.

In previous investigation of eutectic Si-B alloy performed by the author, a continuous SiC barrier layer could be observed along the entire interface between the alloy and crucible. This might result in saturation of the alloy by SiC with time, which ultimately will reduce the fusion enthalpy of the system. No continuous SiC barrier layer could be observed in any of the samples containing Fe-Si-B. However, some SiC and B₄C particles could be observed along the edges of the alloy, in addition to a eutectic B_{4+δ}C phase in several areas of the alloy. The total amount of carbon present in the eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy still appeared to be lower compared to eutectic Si-B alloy. The activity of silicon in the eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy was found to be significantly lower than in eutectic Si-B alloy, which supports the assumption of less SiC formation in eutectic Fe-Si-B. It can thus be

concluded that eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy will remain more stable with time compared to Si-B alloy.

Wetting tests were performed on graphite and alumina. The results showed that Fe-Si-B has a contact angle of approx. 31° on graphite, which indicates high wettability. High wettability might result in more penetration of silicon in the crucible, and consequently faster degradation of the crucible. However, since very little penetration of silicon was observed in the crucible, it appears like the high wettability will not be a challenge in the intended application. The contact angle of Fe-Si-B on alumina was found to be approx. 120° , which indicates low wettability. The reactivity between these materials was also found to be low, and it is thus concluded that alumina might be a possible alternative crucible material for the intended application.

The volume of the Fe-Si-B alloy was found to be shrinking during solidification. Previous challenges has occurred with both pure silicon and eutectic Si-B alloy, in which the crucibles cracked due to volume expansion during solidification. Therefore, the shrinkage in volume during solidification in the Fe-Si-B alloy is considered to be an advantage for the intended application.

The samples in the wetting tests showed signs of melting in the range between 1200-1250 $^\circ\text{C}$, and the slight deviation from the theoretical melting temperature was considered to be due to carbon saturation.

Six different phases were detected by EMPA analysis. This includes FeB and Si_4BFe_4 as matrices, SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$ spread across the entire samples with eutectic composition, and SiC particles located at the edge of the samples. It is uncertain if the two three-component phases, Si_4BFe_4 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}_2$, were metastable, or if they were stable due to carbon saturation of the system. Two modifications of boron carbide were found, namely B_4C and $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$. B_4C was formed as particles in the same areas as SiC, while $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ appeared to have formed at the eutectic temperature in several areas of sample. The $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ was found to contain more boron compared to B_4C , in addition to slightly more aluminium impurities. Small concentrations of aluminium were detected in the entire samples, but with slightly higher concentrations in the SiB_6 phase and in the $\text{B}_{4+\delta}\text{C}$ phase, as mentioned.

The fusion enthalpy of Fe-Si-B with 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si, and 9 wt.% B was calculated in FactSage to be 3.67 kJ/cm³. This is slightly lower than for eutectic Si-B, which has a fusion enthalpy of 4.42 kJ/cm³, but still sufficiently high for the intended application.

The obtained composition of the alloy was confirmed to be close to the ideal composition by ICP-MS analysis. Other than the alloying elements, only very small concentrations of Al and Mn were detected. The results obtained in this work are thus considered to be representative for eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy with 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si, and 9 wt.% B.

The overall results indicate that eutectic Fe-Si-B alloy with 64 wt.% Fe, 26 wt.% Si and 9 wt.% B is highly suitable for the application as phase change material in latent heat thermal energy storage (LHTES) systems, even more so than eutectic Si-B alloy. The results also indicate that alumina might be a possible alternative crucible material for the intended application, and further investigations should be performed.

7 References

- [1] 1414 Degrees (2018). 1414 degrees. <https://1414degrees.com.au>. [Online; accessed 28.02.2018].
- [2] AMADEUS (Jan 2017b). Next generation materials and solid state devices for ultra high temperature energy storage and conversion. <http://amadeus-project.eu/>. [Online; accessed 04.08.2017].
- [3] AMADEUS (Jul 2017a). Amadeus energy storage. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D7huVnCnK8s>. [Online; accessed 06.02.2018].
- [4] Aursjø, S. (2016). Wear of carbon refractory materials in silicon furnaces. Masters thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).
- [5] Aylward, G. H. and Findlay, T. J. V. (2002). *SI Chemical Data*. Wiley, 5th edition.
- [6] Bakke, P. and Klevan, O. S. (1995). Thermodynamics of liquid silicon basis alloys. *Process Techn. Conf. Proc.*, 14:155–165.
- [7] Beaudhuin, M., Chichignoud, G., Bertho, P., Duffar, T., Lemiti, M., and Zaidat, K. (2012). Carbon reaction with levitated silicon – Experimental and thermodynamic approaches. *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, 133 (1):284–288.
- [8] Bjørnstad, E. L. (2016). Mass transfer coefficients and bubble sizes in oxidative ladle refining of silicon. M.sc. thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim.
- [9] Boundless Physics (May 2016). Latent heat. <https://www.boundless.com/physics/textbooks/boundless-physics-textbook/heat-and-heat-transfer-13/phase-change-and-latent-heat-112/latent-heat-397-11289/>. [Online; accessed 27.07.2017].
- [10] Chipman, J., Alfred, R. M., Gott, L. W., Small, R., Wilson, D. M., and Thompson, C. (1952). The solubility of carbon in molten iron and in iron-silicon and iron-manganese alloys. *Trans. ASM.*, 44:1215.
- [11] Ciftja, A. (2009). *Solar silicon refining; Inclusions, settling, filtration, wetting*. PhD thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).
- [12] Computational Thermodynamics Inc. (2011). Metastable iron-carbon (fe-c) phase diagram. <http://www.calphad.com/iron-carbon.html>. [Online; accessed 16.02.2018].
- [13] Crustal Geophysics and Geochemistry Science Center (2013). What is icp-ms?

- <https://crustal.usgs.gov/laboratories/icpms/intro.html>. [Online; accessed 10.05.2018].
- [14] Dalaker, H. (2009). *Solubility of Carbon and Nitrogen in the Silicon Rich Part of the Si-C-N-B-System*. PhD thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).
- [15] Dalaker, H. and Tangstad, M. (2009). Time and Temperature Dependence of the Solubility of Carbon in Liquid Silicon Equilibrated with Silicon Carbide and Its Dependence on Boron Levels. *Materials Transactions*, 50 (5):1152–1156.
- [16] Dash, W. C. (1958). Data referred to by Hall, R. N. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 29:914.
- [17] Datas, A. (2016). Hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic converter. *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, 108.
- [18] Datas, A., Martí, A., del Cañizo, C., Luque, A., and Ciftja, A. (June 2015). Ultra dense latent heat thermal energy storage utilizing high silicon alloys. In *42nd IEEE Photovoltaic Specialists Conference*. Instituto de Energía Solar (IES) (UPM).
- [19] Datas, A., Ramos, A., Martí, A., del Cañizo, C., and Luque, A. (May 2016). Ultra high temperature latent heat energy storage and thermophotovoltaic energy conversion. *Energy*, 107:1,5.
- [20] Datta, A. and Mukherjee, S. (2015). *Structural and Morphological Evolution in Metal-Organic Films and Multilayers*. CRC Press. 18.
- [21] Dolloff, R. T. (Apr 1962). Research Study to Determine the Phase Equilibrium Relations of Selected Metal Carbides at High Temperatures. *WADD TR 60-143 Part 3*, pages 1–37.
- [22] Domnich, V., Reynaud, S., Haber, R. A., and Chowalla, M. (Oct 2011). Boron Carbide: Structure, Properties, and Stability under Stress. *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, 94:1–37.
- [23] Durand, F. and Duby, J. (1999). Carbon solubility in solid and liquid silicon - a review with reference to eutectic equilibrium. *Journal of Phase Equilibria*, 20:61–63.
- [24] Einan, J. (June 2012). Formation of silicon carbide and graphite in the siliconmanganese process. Masters thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology.
- [25] Elliott, J., Gleisser, M., and Ramakrishna, V. (1963). *Thermochemistry for Steel-making*. Addison-Wesley, Pergamon press.
- [26] Ferroatlantica (2018). Ferroglobe. <http://www.ferroatlantica.es>. [Online; ac-

-
- cessed 28.02.2018].
- [27] Gokhale, A. and Abbaschian, G. (1987). The Cr-Si (Chromium-Silicon) System. *Bulletin of Alloy Phase Diagrams*, 8 (5):474.
- [28] Grorud, B. (Dec 2017a). Interaction of liquid si-b alloys with graphite crucibles. Specialisation project, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim.
- [29] Grorud, B. (June 2017b). Interaction of liquid si-b alloys with graphite crucibles. Unpublished, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim.
- [30] Hall, R. N. (1958). Electrical Contacts to Silicon Carbide. *Journal of Applied Physics*, 29:914.
- [31] Hillert, M. (1987). *Metallografisk Atlas*. Institutionen för Metallografi - KTH Stockholm.
- [32] Hjelen, J. (Oct 1986). *Scanning elektron-mikroskopi*. Norges Tekniske Høyskole. 2-3.
- [33] Hoel, E. G. (1995). *Phase relations of Mn-Fe-Si-C systems*. PhD thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).
- [34] Humenik, M. and Kingery, W. D. (1954). Metal-ceramic interactions: Iii, surface tension and wettability of metal-ceramic systems. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 37(1):18.
- [35] Inatomi, Y., Onishi, F., Nagashio, K., and Kuribayashi, K. (2007). Density and Thermal Conductivity Measurements for Silicon Melt by Electromagnetic Levitation under a Static Magnetic Field. *International Journal of Thermophysics*, 28 (1):44–59.
- [36] Ioffe Institute Semiconductors Database (2017). Silicon carbide. thermal properties. <http://www.ioffe.ru/SVA/NSM/Semicond/SiC/thermal.html>. [Online; accessed 02.12.2017].
- [37] Jiao, J. M. (Dec 2017). Thermodynamically properties of Si-B-X (Cu, Fe, Al) system.
- [38] Jiao, J. M., Safarian, J., and Tangstad, M. (To be published in 2018). High temperature interaction of si-b alloys with graphite holder in thermal energy storage systems. *Mat. Met.Trans B*.
- [39] Kasper, B. (1996). *Phasengleichgewichte im system B-C-N-Si*. PhD thesis, Stuttgart University.
- [40] Kenisarin, M. M. (2010). High-temperature phase change materials for thermal energy storage. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 14:955–956, 961.
- [41] Kleykamp, H. and Schumacher, G. (June 1993). The Constitution of the Silicon-Carbon System. *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 97:799–805.

- [42] Kotzé, J. P., von Backström, T. W., and Erens, P. J. (May 2013). High-temperature phase change materials for thermal energy storage. *J. Sol. Energy*, 135(3):1.
- [43] Kubaschewski, O. (1982). *IRON—Binary Phase Diagrams*. Springer-Verlag. 375-384.
- [44] Landolt, H. H. and Börnstein, R. (2004). *Binary Systems from B-C to Cr-ZrB*. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg. 1-2.
- [45] Li, D. and Herlach, D. M. (1996). High undercooling of bulk molten silicon by containerless processing. *Europhysics Letters*, 34 (6).
- [46] Li, J. G. and Hausner, H. (1995). Wetting and infiltration of graphite materials by molten silicon. *Scripta Metallurgica et Materialia*, 32 (3):377–382.
- [47] Liao, P. K. and Spear, K. E. (1986). The B-Cr (Boron-Chromium) system. *Bulletin of Alloy Phase Diagrams*, 7 (3):232–237.
- [48] Massalski, T. (1990). *Binary Alloy Phase Diagrams, Vol. 1*. ASM International. 464.
- [49] Massalski, T. (1996). *Binary alloy phase diagrams, second edition, plus updates*. ASM International.
- [50] Materials Evaluation and Engineering, Inc. (2014). Scanning electron microscopy. <http://www.mee-inc.com/hamm/scanning-electron-microscopy-sem/>. [Online; accessed 03.07.2017].
- [51] Matthew R, G., Scharfe, D. B., Young, M. P., and Webb, R. N. (2014). *High Temperature Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage to Augment Solar Thermal Propulsion for Microsatellites*. PhD thesis, University of Southern California.
- [52] NGU (2005). Xrd-analyser. http://www.ngu.no/upload/Norges%20geologi/NGU-lab/NGU_LAB_XRD_analyser.pdf. [Online; accessed 10.05.2018].
- [53] Nozaki, T., Yatsurugi, Y., and Akiyama, N. (1970). Concentration and Behavior of Carbon in Semiconductor Silicon. *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 112 (12):1566–1568.
- [54] Oden, L. L. and McCune, R. A. (1987). Phase equilibria in the Al-Si-C system. *Metallurgical Transactions A*, 18 (12):2005–2014.
- [55] Olesinski, R. W. and Abbaschian, G. (1984). The C-Si (Carbon-Silicon) System . *Bulletin of Alloy Phase Diagrams*, 5(5):486–489.
- [56] Ottem, L. (1993). Løselighet og termodynamiske data for oksygen og carbon i flytende legeringer av silisium og ferrosilisium, technical report stf24 f93017. SINTEF.

-
- [57] Rubio, Y., Hong, L., Saha-Chaudhury, N., Bush, R., and Sahajwalla, V. (2006). Dynamic wetting of graphite and sic by ferrosilicon alloys and silicon at 1550°C. *ISIJ International*, 46:1570–1576.
- [58] Rubio, Y., Saha-Chaudhury, N., and Sahajwalla, V. (2009). Carbon dissolution occurring during graphite–ferrosilicon interactions at 1550°C. *ISIJ International*, 49:1868–1873.
- [59] Satyendra Kumar Sarna (Nov 2014). Boron in steels. <http://ispatguru.com/boron-in-steels/>. [Online; accessed 16.02.2018].
- [60] Scace, R. I. and Slack, G. A. (1959). Solubility of Carbon in Silicon and Germanium. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*, 30:1551–1555.
- [61] Schei, A., Tunset, J. K., and Tveit, H. (1998). *Production of High Silicon Alloys*. Tapir akademisk forlag. 81.
- [62] Seifert, H. and Aldinger, F. (2002). Phase Equilibria in the Si-B-C-N System. *Structure and Bonding*, 101:1–58.
- [63] SILSTORE (2018). Energy storage for solar energy, electricity and waste heat. <http://silstore.com/index.html>. [Online; accessed 28.02.2018].
- [64] Solberg, J. K. (2016). *Lysmikroskopi*. Institutt for materialteknologi, NTNU. 1.
- [65] Spectro graphic (2017). Optical microscopy. <http://www.spectrographic.co.uk/support/trouble-shooting/>. [Online; accessed 28.06.2017].
- [66] Sun, H., Mori, K., Sahajwalla, V., and Pehlke, R. D. (1998). Carbon solution in liquid iron and iron alloys. *High Temp. Mater. Process.*, 17(4):257.
- [67] Søyland, A.-K. (2004). *Silicon for Solar Cells*. PhD thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).
- [68] Toyo Tanso (2017). Special graphite. http://www.toyotanso.com/Products/Special_graphite/. [Online; accessed 11.11.2017].
- [69] Toyo Tanso Co., LTD. (2017). Property data of ig-15 isotropic graphite. http://www.toyotanso.co.jp/Products/Special_graphite/data_en.html. [Online; accessed 02.12.2017].
- [70] Undheim, E. (2018). *Nucleation and growth of multicrystalline silicon*. PhD thesis, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU).
- [71] University of Tennessee, Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering (2016). The iron–iron carbide (fe–fe₃c) phase diagram. <https://web.utk.edu/~prack/MSE%>

- 20300/FeC.pdf. [Online; accessed 16.02.2018].
- [72] Venkatsrman and Neumann, J. (1990). The C-Cr (Carbon-Chromium) System. *Bulletin of Alloy Phase Diagrams*, 11 (2):152–154.
- [73] W. Werner (2012). Introduction to electron microscopy. <http://coen.boisestate.edu/faculty-staff/files/2012/01/Electrons.pdf>. [Online; accessed 10.05.2018].
- [74] Wu, C. and Sahajwalla, V. (1998). Influence of melt carbon and sulfur on the wetting of solid graphite by Fe-C-S melts. *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions B*, 29(2):471–477.
- [75] Yanaba, K., Akasaka, M., Takeuchi, M., Watanabe, M., Narushima, T., and Iguchi, Y. (1997). Solubility of Carbon in Liquid Silicon Equilibrated with Silicon Carbide. *Materials Transactions, JIM*, 38:990–994.
- [76] Yanaba, K., Matsumura, Y., Narushima, T., and Iguchi, Y. (1998). Effect of Alloying Elements on Carbon Solubility in Liquid Silicon Equilibrated with Silicon Carbide. *Mater. Trans.*, 39 (8):819–823.
- [77] Yupko, V., Gnesin, G., Dyban, Y., Kuz'mina, T. I., Polomoshnov, I. E., and Sichkar, Z. V. (1977). The wetting of self-bonded polycrystalline silicon carbide by silicon I. Effect of phase composition on wetting. *Powder Metall Met Ceram*, 16:777–780.
- [78] Zaitsev, A. and Kodentsov, A. A. (2001). Thermodynamic Properties and Phase Equilibria in the Si-B System. *Journal of Phase Equilibria*, 22(2):126–135.
- [79] Zhao, L. and Sahajwalla, V. (2003). Interfacial phenomena during wetting of graphite/alumina mixtures by liquid iron. *ISIJ International*, 43(1):1–6.
- [80] Zhou, H. and Singh, R. B. (Sep 1995). Kinetics Model for the Growth of Silicon Carbide by the Reaction of Liquid Silicon with Carbon. *Journal of American Ceramic Society*, 78(9):2456–2462.

Appendix A XRD analysis

An XRD analysis was performed on sample 11 and sample 12 by Research Scientist Julian Richard Tolchard, SINTEF Industry. The spectra appeared to be quite different, as seen in Figure A.1, however, they might as well be quite similar. When crystals all grow in one direction certain peaks may become extremely strong, and essentially hide other peaks. It is assumed that this was the case for sample 12. This will disrupt the software to identify phases, as it use intensity as a part of the matching process. The only phase that was identified was FeSi, and also possibly FeSi₂. As earlier mentioned, FeSi was found in the phase diagram, while FeSi₂ was not.

(a) The figure presents the X-ray diffraction spectrum obtained from sample 11.

(b) The figure presents the X-ray diffraction spectrum obtained from sample 12. One peak appeared extremely strong in this spectrum.

Figure A.1: The figure presents the XRD spectra obtained from sample 11 and sample 12. The analysis was conducted by Research Scientist Julian Richard Tolchard, SINTEF Industry.

Appendix B Images obtained in LOM

The crucibles in all samples from successful experiment were investigated in LOM at 2.5x and 10x magnification. Very little SiC formation could be observed in all the crucibles, except for in the Si-B reference sample. It could be observed that the alloy did creep up along the walls to some extent, but the upper parts of the crucible was completely free of alloy and SiC.

B.1 2.5x magnification

The following images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles at 2.5x magnification.

(a) Bottom of the Si-B reference sample, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. Significant amounts of SiC could be observed in the bottom of the crucible.

(b) Bottom of sample 9, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Bottom of sample 10, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Bottom of sample 11, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.1: Images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Except for in the Si-B reference sample, very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Bottom of sample 12, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(b) Bottom of sample 13, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Bottom of sample 14, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Bottom of sample 15, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.2: Images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Bottom of sample 16, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The alloy could not be removed from the crucible in this sample. However, very little SiC was observed in this sample as well.

(b) Bottom of sample 17, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Bottom of sample 18, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Bottom of sample 19, which contained twice the amount of alloy compared to the other samples. The sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.3: Images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

The following images are obtained from the left corner of the crucibles at 2.5x magnification.

(a) Left corner of the Si-B reference sample, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. Some SiC could be observed in the left corner of the crucible.

(b) Left corner of sample 9, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The scratches that can be observed in the crucible occurred during polishing.

(c) Left corner of sample 10, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Left corner of sample 11, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.4: Images are obtained from the left corner of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Except for in the Si-B reference sample, very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Left corner of sample 12, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(b) Left corner of sample 13, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Left corner of sample 14, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Left corner of sample 15, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.5: Images are obtained from the left corner of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Left corner of sample 16, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The alloy could not be removed from the crucible in this sample. However, very little SiC was observed in this sample as well.

(b) Left corner of sample 17, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. A crack in the crucible could be observed in the upper part of the image. The scratch that can be observed in the bottom occurred during polishing.

(c) Left corner of sample 18, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Left corner of sample 19, which contained twice the amount of alloy compared to the other samples. The sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.6: Images are obtained from the left corner of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

The following images are obtained from the left wall of the crucibles at 2.5x magnification.

(a) Left wall of the Si-B reference sample, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. Significant amounts of SiC could be observed in the Left wall of the crucible.

(b) Left wall of sample 9, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The scratches that can be observed in the crucible occurred during polishing.

(c) Left wall of sample 10, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Left wall of sample 11, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.7: Images are obtained from the left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Except for in the Si-B reference sample, very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Left wall of sample 12, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(b) Left wall of sample 13, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Left wall of sample 14, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Left wall of sample 15, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.8: Images are obtained from the left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Left wall of sample 16, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The alloy could not be removed from the crucible in this sample. However, very little SiC was observed in this sample as well.

(b) Left wall of sample 17, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Left wall of sample 18, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Left wall of sample 19, which contained twice the amount of alloy compared to the other samples. The sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.9: Images are obtained from the left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 2.5x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

B.2 10x magnification

The following images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles at 10x magnification.

(a) Bottom of the Si-B reference sample, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. Significant amounts of SiC could be observed in the bottom of the crucible.

(b) Bottom of sample 9, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The scratches that can be observed in the crucible occurred during polishing.

(c) Bottom of sample 10, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Bottom of sample 11, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.10: Images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Except for in the Si-B reference sample, very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Bottom of sample 12, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(b) Bottom of sample 13, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Bottom of sample 14, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Bottom of sample 15, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.11: Images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Bottom of sample 16, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The alloy could not be removed from the crucible in this sample. However, very little SiC was observed in this sample as well.

(b) Bottom of sample 17, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Bottom of sample 18, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Bottom of sample 19, which contained twice the amount of alloy compared to the other samples. The sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.12: Images are obtained from the bottom of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

The following images are obtained from the Corner of the crucibles at 10x magnification.

(a) Corner of the Si-B reference sample, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. Significant amounts of SiC could be observed in the corner of the crucible.

(b) Corner of sample 9, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The scratches that can be observed in the crucible occurred during polishing.

(c) Corner of sample 10, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Corner of sample 11, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.13: Images are obtained from the corner of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Except for in the Si-B reference sample, very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Corner of sample 12, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(b) Corner of sample 13, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Corner of sample 14, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Corner of sample 15, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.14: Images are obtained from the corner of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Corner of sample 16, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The alloy could not be removed from the crucible in this sample. However, very little SiC was observed in this sample as well.

(b) Corner of sample 17, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Corner of sample 18, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Corner of sample 19, which contained twice the amount of alloy compared to the other samples. The sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.15: Images are obtained from the corner of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

The following images are obtained from the lower left wall of the crucibles at 10x magnification.

(a) Left wall of the Si-B reference sample, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. Significant amounts of SiC could be observed in the lower left wall of the crucible.

(b) Lower left wall of sample 9, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The scratches that can be observed in the crucible occurred during polishing.

(c) Lower left wall of sample 10, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Lower left wall of sample 11, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.16: Images are obtained from the lower left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Except for in the Si-B reference sample, very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Lower left wall of sample 12, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(b) Lower left wall of sample 13, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Lower left wall of sample 14, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Lower left wall of sample 15, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.17: Images are obtained from the lower left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Lower left wall of sample 16, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The alloy could not be removed from the crucible in this sample. However, very little SiC was observed in this sample as well.

(b) Lower left wall of sample 17, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Lower left wall of sample 18, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Lower left wall of sample 19, which contained twice the amount of alloy compared to the other samples. The sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.18: Images are obtained from the lower left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

The following images are obtained from the upper left wall of the crucibles at 10x magnification.

(a) Left wall of the Si-B reference sample, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. Significant amounts of SiC could be observed in the upper left wall of the crucible.

(b) Upper left wall of sample 9, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The scratches that can be observed in the crucible occurred during polishing.

(c) Upper left wall of sample 10, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Upper left wall of sample 11, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.19: Images are obtained from the upper left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Except for in the Si-B reference sample, very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Upper left wall of sample 12, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(b) Upper left wall of sample 13, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Upper left wall of sample 14, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Upper left wall of sample 15, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.20: Images are obtained from the upper left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

(a) Upper left wall of sample 16, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The alloy could not be removed from the crucible in this sample. However, very little SiC was observed in this sample as well.

(b) Upper left wall of sample 17, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

(c) Upper left wall of sample 18, which was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$.

(d) Upper left wall of sample 19, which contained twice the amount of alloy compared to the other samples. The sample was kept at 1550 °C for 1h, before being subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure B.21: Images are obtained from the upper left wall of the crucibles by light optical microscope at 10x magnification. Very little SiC could be observed in the crucibles.

Appendix C Images obtained in SEM

All samples from successful experiments were investigated in SEM at different magnifications to investigate how the phases had formed. The following sections provide the images obtained from all samples in SEM.

C.1 Samples subjected to one temperature cycle

The following figures contain images of samples kept at 1550°C for 1h, before they were subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The images were obtained at 50x, 100x, 150x, and 200x magnification in SEM.

The following images are obtained from sample 9.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 9 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 9 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 9 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 9 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure C.1: The figure shows images obtained from sample 9 at different magnifications in SEM.

Sample 9 appeared to contain the same phases that were identified in EPMA. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage.

The following images are obtained from sample 10.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 10 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure C.2: The figure shows images obtained from sample 10 at different magnifications in SEM.

Sample 10 appeared to contain the same phases that were identified in EPMA. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage .

The following images are obtained from sample 16. This sample reacted more with the crucible than the other samples, and the alloy was not possible to remove from the crucible. It was thus possible to investigate the interface between the alloy and the crucible, hence this sample was investigated at 50x, 100x, 200x, and 700x.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 16 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 16 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 16 at 200x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 16 at 700x magnification in SEM. SiC was observed along the bottom of the crucible in this sample.

Figure C.3: The figure shows images obtained from sample 16 at different magnifications in SEM.

Sample 16 appeared to contain the same phases that were identified in EPMA. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage. More SiC was observed at the bottom of this sample compared to all the other samples.

C.2 Samples subjected to two temperature cycles

The following figures contain images of samples kept at 1550°C for 1h, before they were subjected to two temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$. The images were obtained at 50x, 100x, 150x, and 200x magnification in SEM.

The following images are obtained from sample 14.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 14 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 14 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 14 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 14 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure C.4: The figure shows images obtained from sample 14 at different magnifications in SEM.

Sample 14 appeared to contain the same phases that were identified in EPMA. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage.

The following images are obtained from sample 17.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 17 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 17 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 17 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 17 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure C.5: The figure shows images obtained from sample 17 at different magnifications in SEM.

Sample 17 appeared to contain the same phases that were identified in EPMA. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage.

C.3 Samples subjected to a larger temperature interval

The following figures contain images of samples kept at 1550°C for 1h, before they were subjected to one temperature cycle between $T_m \pm 100^\circ\text{C}$. The images were obtained at 50x, 100x, 200x, and 250x magnification in SEM.

The following images are obtained from sample 15.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 15 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 15 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 15 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 15 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure C.6: The figure shows images obtained from sample 15 at different magnifications in SEM.

Sample 15 appeared to contain the same phases that were identified in EPMA. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage. This sample appeared to be more eutectic compared to the samples subjected to temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.

The following images are obtained from sample 18.

(a) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 50x magnification in SEM.

(b) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 100x magnification in SEM.

(c) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 150x magnification in SEM.

(d) The image is obtained from sample 18 at 200x magnification in SEM.

Figure C.7: The figure shows images obtained from sample 18 at different magnifications in SEM.

Sample 18 appeared to contain the same phases that were identified in EPMA. The structure of the phases indicates that SiB_6 and $\text{Si}_2\text{B}_5\text{Fe}$ are eutectic phases, while FeB and Si_4BFe_4 precipitated at an earlier stage. This sample appeared to be more eutectic compared to the samples subjected to temperature cycles between $T_m \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$.